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POST BURN PRURITUS RELIEF PROTOCOL

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ABSTRACT

Post burn pruritus is pervasive, occurring in over 90% of burn patients. Moreover, post burn pruritus continues in greater than 40% of patients for years even after burn wounds are healed. Post burn pruritus is a syndrome of stressful symptoms experienced by burn survivors that requires medical management with effective interventions. Unfortunately, many burn patients suffer from pruritus-related post burn injury regardless of current standard therapies. Therefore, in this Doctor of Nursing Practice project, published evidence including studies/reviews of post burn pruritus relief served as a basis for development of an advanced practice nurse (APN)-driven post burn pruritus relief protocol. A systematic review was conducted and relevant empiric articles from September 1, 2013 to November 17, 2014 were critically appraised. Initially, 79 articles were found; 38 articles were selected using pre-established inclusion criteria. Two frameworks were used to guide this project. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) model was applied for the literature review and the Rosswurm and Larrabee's model for evidence-based practice change was used for clinical application. The newly developed APN driven post burn pruritus protocol is driven by burn healing phase (pre-healing, healing, post-healing), and emphasizes non-pharmacological interventions; it includes both non-pharmacological and pharmacological methods specifically intended for reducing burn associated pruritus.

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BACKGROUND

In 1992, a Burn Nursing Delphi study classified pruritus as one of the highest priority areas in nursing research. However, there has been a lack of research examining the etiology and treatment of this highly distressing symptom (Goutos, 2010). Multiple studies (Carrougner et al., 2013; Goutos, Clarke, Upson, Richardson, & Ghosh, 2010; Goutos, Dziewulski, & Richardson, 2009) have examined post burn pruritus or itching and have varying findings. Each study, however, has consistently demonstrated a considerable level of pruritus in post burn populations. Casaer, Kums, Wouters, Van den Kerckhove and Van den Berghe (2008) reported that 49% of patients, even with small burn injury, experienced pruritus. Post burn pruritus can be defined as a severe itching sensation as a result of burn injury. Pruritus has been identified as one of the most general debilitating and stressful symptoms that post burn survivors experience (Bell & Gabriel, 2009; Goutos, 2010; Goutos, Dziewulski, & Richardson, 2009).

The prevalence of post burn pruritus is seen in over 90% of burn patients and can persist in greater than 40% of those patients for 4 to 10 years after burn injury (Carrougner et al., 2013). According to Brooks et al. (2008), among patients with four years after burn injury, 79% reported intermittent problems with pruritus while 29% of patients reported persistent itching. However, twelve years after injury, these numbers decreased to 44% and 5%, respectively.

According to Carrougner et al. (2013), itching prevalence is highly correlated with females, young age, large burn areas, more grafted areas, dry skin, and raised or thick scars. Casaer et al. (2008) more precisely reported that patients experienced more pruritus between the ages of 2 to 50 years old; if the burn area was large; and, the area of

burn injury was on the trunk rather than the extremities. On the other hand, a study by Thompson et al. (2013) found no significant differences between age and gender regarding hypertrophic scars and pruritus. Thompson et al. (2013) reported burn size over 20% of total body surface area (TBSA) had increased risk of itching. Yang et al. (2014) found that patients with post burn pruritus had broader burned areas and more severe scars. According to Goutos et al. (2009), burn patients tend to have significant amount of itching within 1 month after burn injury with the highest at 6 months and a decline over the first year after the injury. They reported that the origin of a burn can affect associated pruritus. For example, scald injuries were most likely to provoke pruritus, followed by flame and contact injuries (Goutos et al., 2009). The reason for different findings from different studies was each study had different population characteristics regarding TBSA, ages, gender, and burn areas. However, larger size of burns are obviously more associated with post burn pruritus according to these studies (Carrougner et al., 2013; Casaer et al., 2008; Thompson et al., 2013).

Post burn pruritus negatively impacts the quality of life in patients that included; sleep disturbances, decreased enjoyment with leisure activities, decreased ability to complete activities of daily living, and decreased school and work performance (Hettrick et al., 2004). In addition, about 60% of burn patients experienced difficulty falling asleep (Carrougner et al., 2013). According to Casaer et al. (2008), burn patients' daily life was impacted in 42% of those suffering from moderate pruritus and 92% of those suffering from severe pruritus. Parnell, Nedelec, Rachelska and LaSalle (2012) reported that pruritus was related to low concentration, agitation, anxiety, and flat mood. In general,

researchers reported that pruritus triggered negative quality of life associated with dryness, heat, sweat, activity, stress, fatigue, physical effort, and special fabric.

The problem of pruritus in post burn patients is well recognized. There are many potential treatments available for itching (Bell & Gabriel, 2009). However, none of the current standard therapies have been very effective (Otene & Onumaegbu, 2013). In addition, there is currently no accord on standardized treatment of post burn pruritus (Otene & Onumaegbu, 2013; Richardson, Upton & Rippon, 2014). Most often, therapies include pharmacological interventions that include a selective histamine receptor antagonist, but it is effective in only about 20% of patients (Brooks, Malic, & Judkins, 2008). This is because histamine is not the only element involved in the mechanism of itching, but also there are non-histamine dependent pathways involved in the pruritus mechanism according to the study by Schmelz (as cited in Brooks et al., 2008). Another treatment is emollients which also have limited usage. For example, a eutectic mixture of local anesthetic (EMLA) cream can be applied only to healed skin and the maximum zone treated is 600 cm² for patients less than 19 kg and 2000 cm² for patients greater than 20 kg (Brooks et al., 2008). This lack of effective care is further compounded by the absence of a standardized protocol. The Burn Nursing Delphi study (1992) identified the need for high impact potential antipruritic strategies to improve patient care (Goutos et al., 2009).

Problem Statement

Post burn pruritus has been identified as one of the most general and stressful symptoms that burn survivors experience and should be aggressively managed (Bell & Gabriel, 2009; Goutos, 2010; Goutos, Dziewulski, & Richardson, 2009). Pruritus from

post burn injury begins in the early stages of wound healing. Pruritus is usually prominent in patients who have second degree burns, but patients who experience third degree burns may also have partly second degree burns. Pruritus comes along with wound healing in the first two weeks after burn injury (Bell & Gabriel, 2009). Consistently research findings have strongly proposed that post burn pruritus management should be one of the top priorities for burn research (Bell & Gabriel, 2009; Brooks, Malic, & Judkins, 2008). Itching from associated burn injury that persists over a period of time leads to disabling symptoms such as sleep disturbance, anxiety, and interruption of daily activities (Goutos et al., 2009).

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this project was to develop an advanced practice nurse (APN) driven post burn pruritus relief protocol that include pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions in outpatient settings. This protocol would be used for patients experiencing post burn associated pruritus. Expected outcome of the protocol would be a reduction in post burn pruritus as determined by the 5 D Itch Scale and Visual Analogue Scale (VAS). This project has three objectives: 1) to conduct a systematic literature review; 2) identify non pharmacological and pharmacological relief interventions; and 3) identify an implementation change model for clinical practice.

The target population for this project was all patients experiencing pruritus from second and third degree burns in various stages of wound healing. This project included post burn patients. The desired outcomes and benefits of this post burn pruritus protocol will improve the quality of life in patients with burn injuries (Casaer et al., 2008).

Supporting Framework

This project used two supporting frameworks: the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) model and the Rosswurm and Larrabee's model for evidence-based practice change. Further discussion of these models will be discussed in this paper.

The purpose of this project was to construct a post burn pruritus relief protocol through a systemic literature review to develop a protocol in order to improve the quality of life in burn patients. The PRISMA model used to improve the reporting of systematic reviews and meta-analyses was used as the standard guideline for this systematic review (Liberati et al., 2009).

The Rosswurm and Larrabee's model of evidence-based practice change was also used as an appropriate conceptual framework for evidence based practice in this project. The model incorporates principles of quality improvement, use of team work tools, and evidence-based translation strategies to support implementation of a new practice (Melnik & Fineout-Overholt, 2011). In this project, developing a post burn pruritus protocol will promote quality care and improve patient outcomes. These frameworks were explained in the methods section of this project and is also integrated in reporting the results.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Overview

Bell and Gabriel (2009) reported the treatment of pruritus after burn injury by reviewing ten research articles that were clinical trials that included nine class II and one class III studies. Class II studies are reliable data that includes observational studies, cohort studies, prevalence studies, and case control studies. Class III studies, on the other hand, contain evidence provided by clinical series, comparative studies, case reviews, case reports, and expert opinion. According to their review, both pharmacologic and non-pharmacological methods significantly decreased post burn pruritus. Effective pharmacologic methods are selective antihistamine antagonists (cetirizine/cimetidine) in adult & pediatric population, Atarax and colloidal oatmeal (topical agent) in adult population, Gabapentin and EMLA (topical agent) in pediatric population. Effective non-pharmacologic methods contain pulsed dye laser and silicone gel sheeting in adult and pediatric patients, and massage and transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS) in adult population. Bell and Gabriel (2009) suggested using moisturizing cream for all patients with post burn pruritus with different treatment plans based on the size of TBSA. According to the review by Goutos, Clarke, Upson, Richardson, and Ghosh (2010), a multidisciplinary approach is necessary in successful assessment and treatment. They recommended early use of centrally acting agents and peripherally acting agents as well as non-pharmacological interventions for the treatment of post burn pruritus in adult and pediatric populations. Rowley-Conwy (2014) also reported emollient cream, cool baths, pressure garments, and oral and topical antihistamines and analgesics were effective in decreasing burn associated pruritus. Rowley-Conwy (2014) also supported

multidisciplinary team to manage burn patients' recovery for the best outcomes of physical, emotional, and psychological aspects.

Goutos, Dziewulski, and Richardson (2009) suggested therapeutic strategies should be classified by interventions on peripheral & central aspects of the pruritic pathway. Interventions that focus on the peripheral aspects of burns are: cooling of the wound; antihistamines; topical Doxepin; local anesthetics; colloidal oatmeal; Capsaicin; Laser therapy; Aloe Vera; topical Dapsone; Unna boot; Compression garments; and, Ondansteron. Centralized interventions are Gabapentin; TENS; massage therapy; and, psychological support (Goutos et al., 2009; Zachariah et al., 2011).

Findings for treatments to relieve post burn pruritus have been developed from several research studies and included diverse methods. However, there was only one suggested protocol found in the literature. This protocol focused on pharmacological methods and required physician orders. Therefore, this project has conducted a systemic review to develop a nurse driven post burn pruritus relief protocol.

Pharmacological Topical Interventions

Pharmacological interventions are often used to relieve pruritus in burn patients. The first drug of choice for pruritus is antihistaminic drugs, especially, H₁ antihistamines; approximately 90.91% of burn patients have had antihistamines prescribed for post burn pruritus (Goutos, 2010). According to Casaer et al. (2008), 23.3% of 258 adult and pediatric burn patients in clinical settings received antihistamines during their research study; and, those treated with antihistamines recalled that they felt reduced pruritus after the treatment. However, because participants also had ointments applied for pruritus, it was unclear how effective antihistamines alone were in decreasing pruritus. Ratcliff et

al. (2005) evaluated the effectiveness of a pharmaco-therapeutic protocol for pain, anxiety, and itching among 286 acute pediatric burn patients in the hospital setting. They reported that 39.2% of participants received medication to control itching at the beginning, but eventually all the children took some type of oral itch medication because their burn wound itching intensity increased as the wound progressed. Ratcliff et al. (2005) accordingly recommended based on their research findings (1) moisturizing body shampoo, lotions, and topical ointments (not hydrocortisone creams); (2) Diphenhydramine 1.25mg/kg/dose orally every six hours; (3) if itch remains poorly controlled, subsequently add Hydroxyzine 0.6mg/kg/dose every 6hours, then Cyproheptadine 0.1mg/g/dose orally every six hours so that one of the medications could be given every two hours.

Goutos (2010) stated that combination of H₁ antihistamines and H₂ antihistamines significantly decreased pruritus compared to using only H₁ antihistamines. Goutos (2010) mentioned a combination of moisturization and three first generation H₁ antihistamines was effective in 84% of acute burn inpatients. Second generation antihistamines are not used for pruritus because first generation antihistamines are commonly used for sedative effect as well as for pruritus relief.

The study by Goutos (2010) demonstrated that 10 out of 22 burn units used additional pharmacological agent. Of the 10 units, 6 units used a second antihistamine, 1 used Ondansetron (serotonin receptor antagonist), and 3 used gabapentin with alone or combining with an antihistamine. Gabapentin has been more effective relieving pruritus in acutely burn patients than first generation antihistamines; especially, Chlorpheniramine (Goutos, 2010).

Ahuja and Gupta (2012) compared the use of Pregabalin to other medicine in managing post burn pruritus for 80 adult patients in outpatient setting. They reported that the group using both antihistamine and Pregabalin and the group using Pregabalin only showed higher rates of remission of itching in post burn population compared to the group of using antihistamine only. However, in the population of mild itching, using both antihistamine and Pregabalin had a much higher rate (77.5%) than using only Pregabalin (23.3%) regarding reducing itching.

Akhtar & Brooks (2012) explored the effect of botulinum toxin (Botox®) as a new agent in managing post burn pruritus and found that Botox® successfully decreased pruritus in 8 outpatient adult burn population who were resistant to conventional therapies. All eight post burn patients described itching as “0” out of 10 at 2 weeks after Botox® injection. The average duration of no pruritus after the treatment was 9 months.

The study of Baker et al. (2001) demonstrated the combination of histamine 1 (H1) receptor blocker and histamine 2 (H2) receptor blockers significantly reduced post burn pruritus than using H1 receptor blocker only during the first 4 days of treatment in 17 adult and pediatric patients. After 4 days of treatment, there were no differences between two cases. Baker et al. (2001) also reported that programmed (scheduled) medication rather than medication on demand (PRN) contributed to the reduction of pruritus. The review by Goutos (2013) also reported that aggressive antihistamine was effective in the early phase, but in the later stages wounds appeared to be less effective to antihistamine therapy.

Mendham's (2004) study was done to test the action of gabapentin on itching in healing wounds among 35 children admitted to the inpatient burn unit. The research

sample was the population who had been treated with Chlorpheniramine and Trimeprazine, but still remained irritable and constantly itching wounds at the beginning of the research. Gabapentin was given starting as 5mg/kg three times a day and maximum dose increased up to 5mg/kg twice a day and 10mg/kg at night. Within 24 hours of gabapentin use, parents and nursing staff assessed the effects of the treatment and they stated that there was a remarkable reduction in itching and they had decreased or unused antihistamine intake.

Ahuja, Gupta, Gupta, and Shrivastava (2010), studied the effectiveness of gabapentin in decreasing post burn pruritus comparing to using cetirizine alone and combination of gabapentin and cetirizine for 28days in 20 burn patients with ages of 12 to 70 years. The study showed that using gabapentin alone reduced itching in 95% of people in the group while cetirizine alone used group and combination of gabapentin and cetirizine used group reduced itching to 52% and 94%, respectively. In addition, the study demonstrated that the onset of action with gabapentin was significantly faster than the cetirizine. According to Ahuja et al. (2010), 74% in gabapentin group stated the relief of pruritus whereas 32% in the group with cetirizine alone stated pruritus relief on the third day after the treatment. Ahuja et al. (2010) suggested the need for pruritus relief protocol as well as the need for appropriate dosage of gabapentin treatment was needed to reduce post burn pruritus.

Goutos, Eldardiri, Khan, Dziewulski, and Ricahrdson (2010) compared gabapentin treatment with antihistamine treatment in relieving acute post burn pruritus among 91 adult and pediatric burn population of inpatient setting. Gabapentin monotherapy was four times more effective than Chlorpheniramine monotherapy in acute

burn pruritus (41.46% vs 10%). As an antipruritic polytherapy in acute burns, combination of gabapentin, cetirizine and Cyproheptadine was more effective than the combination of three antihistamines (Chlorpheniramine, Hydroxyzine, and Cyproheptadine) in relief rate of pruritus in post burn population. The outcome was 95.12% and 84%, respectively. Goutos et al. (2010) also suggested polytherapy in younger population and larger TBSA because monotherapy had higher failure rate in younger populations.

Anand (2012) showed the effectiveness of gabapentin for pruritus in palliative care, too. According to the literature review by Anand (2012), gabapentin is safe and effective in uremic pruritus, cancer and hematologic causes, opioid-induced itch, brachioradial pruritus, burns pruritus, and pruritus of unknown origin. In the study by Goutos (2013), gabapentin had persistent therapeutic effect because of the ability to prevent central nervous system sensitization; Ondansetron was more effective in reducing pruritus than antihistamine; serotonin had pruritus relief effect; and TENS was more effective in reducing post burn pruritus during the remodeling phase. Warner, Coffee, and Yowler (2014) supported efficient outpatient burn management by using H-1 receptor blocking agent (cetirizine) during the early stage of pruritus as scheduled basis not as needed basis combined with frequent massage of moisturizers. In addition, neuro-inflammatory transmitter blockers (Gabapentin and Pregabalin) are effective because they prevent neuron transmitters from stimulating itch-specific neurons (Warner et al., 2014).

The study by Otene and Onumaegbu (2013) revealed that 88.6% of 35 plastic surgeons had no assessment tool or method to evaluate post burn pruritus while only

11.4% believed they had a method of assessing the severity of post-burn pruritus. Otene and Onumaegbu (2013) also stated that “57.1% would use oral medications as first-line treatment, 22.9% would use injectables, 8.6% would use topical agents, 5.7% would only reassure the patients and another 5.7% would use a combination of oral and topical agents together. 85.7% of these plastic surgeons and burn care specialists did not have any form of anti-pruritic regimen, as only 14.3% indicated having this”. Otene and Onumaegbu (2013) recommended Itch Man Scale as an assessment tool for pruritus and suggested rough guidelines as a pruritus relief management according to the score measured by Itch Man Scale.

According to the review by Brooks et al. (2008), topical agents such as capsaicin and nanocrystalline silver ointment can be used to reduce pruritus. These drugs can also be used as part of a combination therapy. Topical steroid, Doxepin or Dothiepin cream (a tricyclic antidepressant), and EMLA can be used as part of a combination therapy in pharmacological interventions.

One topical agent, Provase®, is a nonprescription moisturizer with a blend of protease enzymes. Nedelec, Rachelska, Parnell and LaSalle (2012) performed a prospective, double-blind, randomized, controlled, and pilot study to evaluate the effect of Provase® in reducing post burn pruritus in 18 burn patients. According to Nedelec et al. (2012), the application of Provase® to post burn population significantly reduced the duration and the frequency of pruritus, area of itch, and the presence of affective itch characteristics. For instance, treatment group reported the area of itch was decreased to half after four weeks of Provase® application.

La Salle, Rachelska, and Nedelec (2007) evaluated the effect of naltrexone in managing post burn pruritus among 13 adult population in inpatient and outpatient settings. They reported research participants who had failed with H1 or H2 receptor antagonist and hydrating lotion demonstrated some satisfaction of naltrexone use in reducing post burn pruritus. Overall, 50% of research participants improved the frequency and duration of itching, 72% were satisfied with the itch relief provided by naltrexone, and 62% stated that quality of life improved by using naltrexone. Jung et al. (2009) did a study to determine the effects of naltrexone as a potential antipruritic medication for 19 adult burn population in the inpatient setting experiencing chronic refractory itching. All of the research subjects were population who had failed in reducing post burn pruritus with antihistamine, gabapentin, or both antihistamine and gabapentin before. However, researchers found out that 44.5% (9 patients) of research subjects reported decreased scratching activity two weeks after using naltrexone.

Mugwort lotion seems to be effective in treating the itch associated with post burn pruritus who had hypertrophic scars (Ogawa & Hyakusoku, 2008). Mugwort lotion significantly decreased pruritus, sleep disturbance and redness after 2 months of treatment in 14 adult post burn patients of inpatient setting suffering from hypertrophic scars in the study by Ogawa & Hyakusoku (2008).

Lewis et al. (2012) explored the efficacy of Medilixir (mixture of coconut, palm, castor, olive, hemp seed, wheat germ, and canola seed oil) compared to the standard treatment of aqueous cream (mixture of paraffin, heavy liquid, phenoxyethanol, and purified water) regarding relieving the post burn itch symptoms. Research findings

indicate that Medilixir is more effective in minimizing post burn pruritus than aqueous cream in 52 adult burn population of inpatient setting.

Campanati et al. (2013) evaluated the clinical effect of the topical application of Ozonated oil on second degree skin burns comparing to the treatment with hyaluronic acid gel. Thirty adult patients were applied Ozonated oil on half of the burn lesion and hyaluronic acid on the other half of the lesion once a day for 12weeks. Clinical features of each lesion (erythema, tension, height, itching, and burning sensation) were assessed at baseline, six, and twelve months after treatment. Ozonated oil had the same efficacy of hyaluronic acid in reducing symptoms related to burns (erythema, tension, height, itching, and burning sensation) after 12 weeks of topical application.

Non-Pharmacological Interventions

Studies that have non-pharmacological interventions in relieving pruritus for burn population include: psychological interventions, massage therapy, silicone sheeting for burn wounds, hypnosis, TENS (transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation), and Unna boot application (Brooks et al., 2008). Cold water, cold temperature, and rest also can relieve pruritus in some burn population (Parnell et al., 2012). The study by Goutos (2010) found that 2 out of 22 burn units utilized psychologists, 2 units used massage therapy, and 1 unit used silicone products for pruritic wounds and these methods were effective in reducing pruritus in burn patients.

According to Upton, Penn, Richardson, and Rippon (2014), psychological approaches are effective in reducing wound itching. Upton et al. (2014) reviewed 12 published articles regarding psychological methods (habit reversal, suggestions, relaxation training, massage, and itch-coping programs) are used to treat wound

associated pruritus. The study finding demonstrated psychological methods reduced itching but this approach was supported by only one article. Psychological interventions can be applied with consultation of a psychologist in conjunction with other therapies.

Muscle relaxation methods decrease itching in burn populations. Farahanil, Hekmatpou, and Khani (2013) investigated the effect of muscle relaxation on pain, pruritus, and vital signs among 110 hospitalized adult and pediatric patients suffering from burns. They assessed pain, pruritus, and vital signs before and after the Benson relaxation method was applied. According to the study, muscle relaxation technique was effective in relieving the pain, pruritus, and vital signs of patients suffering from burns.

Brooks, Phang, and Moazzam (2007) performed a case study with 5 cases including 7, 20, 40, 45, and 65% of TBSA having mixed-thickness burns from both inpatient and outpatient clinic and reported the effect of Acticoat® (Nanocrystalline silver) for itch relief in burn patients. Acticoat® was applied for 2 weeks and the intervals from original injury to application were 2, 3, 3, 6, and 8 months. Before and after 2 weeks of application, Visual Analog Scale (VAS) of itching was assessed and compared. VAS score was 7.4 before application and it decreased to 3.1 after application of Acticoat® ($p = 0.002$) which significantly reduced post burn pruritus. However, the study did not indicate the condition of wounds. For example, whether the burns were healed or unhealed was not stated. It is assumed they were unhealed or in the healing process because Acticoat® is used for unhealed wounds in current practice.

Field et al. (2000) performed a randomized controlled trial (RCT) to evaluate the effect of massage therapy in reducing post burn itching, pain, and psychological symptoms of 20 adult burn patients in the outpatient setting suffering from pruritus. The

research finding is massage therapy significantly decreases itching, pain, depression, and anxiety in post burn population with severe itching. According to Gurol, Polat, and Akcay (2010), massage therapy effectively alleviates pruritus in 63 burn adolescent inpatients even though this application is not commonly used. Pfab et al. (2013) reported in their review that 15 minute massage therapy twice a week over 5 weeks reduced itching, pain, and anxiety levels in burn adolescents. The study by Cho et al. (2014) reported the effect of burn rehabilitation massage therapy on 146 adult inpatients with hypertrophic scars after acute burn care. Their findings indicated that burn massage therapy is effective in improving pain, pruritus, and scar characteristics in hypertrophic scars after burn (Cho et al, 2014).

TENS is known as an ideal method of treating itching. The case study by Whitaker (2001) exhibited the effect of TENS in decreasing post burn pruritus. Whitaker (2001) applied TENS to a 19 year old patient at the inpatient setting who suffered from severe itching after being healed from 70% mixed thickness flame burns. After two weeks of using the TENS unit in the study, the patient did not need to continue the use of the TENS unit because post burn pruritus no longer existed. Hettrick (2004) evaluated the effect of TENS as the management of burn pruritus in a pilot study with RCT on 20 adult burn patients in the outpatient setting and reported TENS significantly reduced post burn pruritus in the population sampled. In the study, Hettrick applied one hours of TENS per day, 7 days a week for 3 weeks to the experimental group. It was suggested that TENS should be considered as a treatment option for burn survivors whose quality of life was negatively affected by itching (Hettrick, 2004).

Silicone gel sheeting is considered effective in reducing scar pigmentation, pain, and itching as well as improving scar thickness and pliability (Li-Sang, Lau, Choi, Chan, & Jianan, 2006). The study by Li-Sang et al. (2006) demonstrated significant efficacy of silicone gel sheeting on severe post-traumatic hypertrophic scars among 45 Chinese adult outpatient burn population in their RCT. In a similar study, Li-Tsang, Zheng, and Lau (2010) investigated the effect of pressure therapy, silicone gel sheeting, and combined therapy on management of posttraumatic hypertrophic scar among 104 adult and pediatric burn population in the outpatient setting. All three methods significantly reduced itching but silicone gel sheeting had better results but was not statistically significant (Li-Sang et al., 2010).

Laser therapy is one of ways to relieve pruritus. According to pretest and posttest designed study by Gaida et al. (2003), low level laser therapy (LLLT) was effectively decreased pain and pruritus in 19 adult post burn population of the outpatient setting. Likewise, Hultman, Edkins, Wu, Calvert, and Cairns (2013) reported that laser therapy on burn scars significantly improved pain, pruritus, pliability, and paresthesia among 147 outpatients ($P < 0.0001$).

Waked, Nagib, and Ashm (2013) evaluated the effectiveness of triamcinolone acetate phonophoresis (TAP) compared to TENS in the treatment of post burn pruritus for 40 adult inpatients. According to the researchers, there was a significant improvement in reducing pruritus in both group with TAP and the group with TENS ($P < 0.05$). However, there was no significant difference between the two groups regarding the effect of pruritus reduction.

Richardson, Upton and Rippon (2014) suggested an algorithm for the mechanism-based treatment of post burn pruritus based on the stages of healing. According to the algorithm by Richardson et al. (2014), there are four stages that include: inflammatory, inflammatory/proliferative, proliferative/remodeling, and remodeling. Each stage has different treatment methods. However, this algorithm is the only algorithm suggested and requires validation with further use in multiple studies.

Summary of Literature Review

Summary of the literature review shows that Oral anti-pruritic medications are the first drug of choice and they can be given as a scheduled dose by combining with other anti-pruritic medications to be more effective in decreasing pruritus in post burn wounds regardless of wound healing stages. In addition, topical agents decrease post burn pruritus in healed wounds, especially, hypertrophic scars. These topical agents can be used with oral anti pruritic medications or after oral anti-pruritic medications have failed to relieve post burn pruritus.

In addition, non-pharmacological interventions decreased post burn pruritus as effectively as pharmacological interventions. Effective non-pharmacological interventions were psychological intervention (habit reversal, suggestions, relaxation training, and itch-coping programs), pressure therapy, laser therapy, TAP, TENS, Massage, special dressing (silicone sheeting, Nanocrystallin [Acticoat®], and Unna boot), hypnosis, cold water, cold temperature, and rest. However, pharmacological interventions were suggested to augment non-pharmacological interventions to maximize the effect.

This literature review analyzed 38 articles regarding post burn pruritus. 23 articles among them used VAS as a pruritus assessment tool, two articles used Itch man scale, two articles used both Itch man scale and VAS, and two articles used 5-D Itch scale. On the other hand, nine articles did not clearly state which pruritus assessment tool was used. Moreover, each treatment method was supported by less than five studies and most studies were relatively small sample size.

METHODS

Methods for this project included incorporating two models, the PRISMA model and the Rosswurm and Larrabee model of evidence-based practice change. Consistent with a systematic review, a table of evidence (TOE) was used for organization of the research studies (Appendix C). Methods contain: search strategy, eligibility criteria, study selection, data collection process, data extraction, quality assessment, and results.

PRISMA Model

This project partly adopted the PRISMA flow diagram during the process of study selection and data collection. By using the PRISMA flow diagram, the selecting process of studies in this project was transparent. Steps for selecting research studies are identified in the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1), and includes: identification, screening, eligibility check, and inclusion of data.

The PRISMA model for organizing and reporting systematic reviews includes an abstract, background, problem statement, purpose statement, methods, results, and discussion sections. These steps will be clearly delineated as headings throughout this paper. In the health sciences, 174 journals have used the PRISMA model for reporting systematic reviews and meta-analysis in their collections (Moher et al., 2009).

The PRISMA model has also been considered as an assessment tool for research dissemination within the Enhancing the Quality and Transparency of Health Care Research (EQUATOR). The EQUATOR is an international initiative that seeks to improve reliability and value of health related research by promoting accurate and clear reporting of research studies (International Prospective Register of Systemic Reviews, 2009).

Figure 1. PRISMA 2009 flow diagram (Moher, Liberati, Tetzlaff, & Altman, 2009).

The Model for Evidence-based Practice Change

Another framework for this project is the model for evidence-based practice change. This model, published by Rosswurm and Larrabee (1999), was a model used to change practice in an organization (Melnik & Fineout-Overholt, 2011) and is closely related to the PRISMA model in that steps overlap.

The Rosswurm and Larrabee model was based on theoretical and empirical literature related to evidence-based practice, research utilization, standardized language, and change theory. In this model, practitioners are guided through the entire process of

developing and integrating an evidence-based practice change. The model supports evidence-based practice changes derived from a combination of quantitative and qualitative data, clinical expertise, and contextual evidence (Rosswurm & Larrabee, 1999). Because the purpose of this project was to develop a protocol to improve post burn pruritus and related symptoms, the model for evidence-based practice change was an appropriate framework for practice (Figure 2).

In this model, step one included the background, problem statement, and literature review. In addition, step one assessed the need for change in practice by identifying the problem, inclusion of stakeholders, data collection of current practice, and development of a population-intervention-comparison-outcome- and time frame (PICOT). Step two was to locate the best evidence by identifying types and sources of evidence, reviewing research concepts, planning the search, and conducting the search (Table 1). Step three analyzed the evidence. This step included appraisal of the evidence, syntheses of the best evidence, and assessment of feasibility, benefits, and the risks of new practice. This project established incorporated step three under literature review and result. Step four was to design practice change and the development of a post burn pruritus relief protocol was the outcome of this step, and the protocol is contained in the results section. For the purposes of this time-limited DNP project steps five and six were not included and developing of a post burn pruritus relief protocol was sufficient, but this protocol will be tested in future research studies.

Figure 2. A model of evidence-based practice change (Larrabee, 2009).

Search Strategy

Four data bases: Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials, CINAHL the Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature, EBSCO, and PubMed were searched. In addition, The National Guideline Clearinghouse, and the following websites: Bandolier, The National Health Service (NHS) Center for Reviews and Dissemination, google scholar, and the American Burn Association (ABA) web site were

used for searching data. Research articles were searched from September 1, 2013 to November 17, 2014. Key words linked with Boolean “AND” included burn(s), itch(ing), itch(es), pruritus, and pruritic.

Data Extraction and Quality Assessment

In accordance with the PRISMA guidelines, articles were collected, studies reviewed for validity, potential bias, and threats. This review also included reviewing the articles for clarity of the clinical question, inclusion criteria, the relevance of the clinical question, study design, data collection, and analysis methods.

Eligibility Criteria

According to the Iowa Model, systematic literature review was performed by formulating a focused clinical question about post burn pruritus (Holly, 2014). The question in the project is “In populations with burn injury, what measures are effective in minimizing post burn pruritus?” Initially, studies published within last five to seven years were inclusion criteria, but there were insufficient literature during the period. Therefore, the criteria for eligibility was expanded to all published studies written in English from 2000 to 2014 that performed on all second and third degree burn population suffering from burn related pruritus to collect sufficient data for the project.

Study Selection and Data Collection Process

Purpose, design, sample, setting, findings of each study were recorded for the studies that were included in this review. Each paper was reviewed and analyzed descriptively. The systemic literature search of articles indicated that 38 studies met the inclusion criteria. A total of 79 articles were searched and 41 articles were excluded according to the flow diagram (Figure 3). First four articles were excluded; one was

written in German, one was only response to the editor of the other article, and the other two articles were reviewed in other articles (duplication of research findings).

Figure 3. Flow diagram for selection of studies.

Next 22 studies were removed conforming to eligibility criteria: Seventeen articles were related only to scar, skin condition, and scar assessment; two studies were only regarding sleep quality in burn patients; and three articles stated general burns and their treatment only. Five articles were excluded because they were written about pruritus assessment tool development and evaluation only. Also, another study was not included because it stated general wound itching instead of writing specifically about post burn associated itching. Nine articles were excluded because they described only pruritus and did not write pruritus relief methods. Therefore, 38 articles were reviewed to

develop a post burn pruritus relief protocol and significant findings of each study were shown in Table 1. Details of each publication was written in the Table of Evidence (TOE) under Appendix B. The TOE was constructed according to purpose, design, sample, setting, operational definition, findings, limitation of each study, and comments. A synthesis of each study was reported at the end of the review of literature.

Table 1

Characteristics of Included Studies

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
1	Ahuja & Gupta (2012)	Outpatient setting / 80 Adult Burn pts	RCT / 28 days	TBSA > 5%, 2 nd degree burns, & wound either in healing (80% epithelialized) or healed	VAS	Pregabalin alone or combined antihistamine w/pregabalin → ↓ PBP Addition of antihistamines does not decrease PBP Massage therapy can be used as adjunctive treatment
2	Ahuja Gupta, Gupta, & Shrivastava (2010)	Single site (department of burns) 20 Burn pts from 12-70 yrs old	RCT / 28 days	TBSA > 5%, 2 nd degree burns, over 80% of wound epithelialized or healed	VAS	Gabapentin alone or combination of gabapentin & cetirizine → ↓ PBP Certirizine only does not decrease PBP
3	Akhtar & Brooks (2012)	Outpatient setting/ 8 pts w/ failure of managing PBP in the past	Prospective & experimental study/ One time	All healed areas after 2 nd - 3 rd degree burns	VAS	Botox → ↓ PBP in the population who failed in managing PBP w/ conventional therapies/ 50% had no PBP within 2wks after Botox treatment/ free of itching up to average 9 months after treatment.
4	Anand (2012)	Varied/ Total number of literature not stated	Literature Review / varied	Not specified	Not stated	Gabapentin → ↓ PBP & ↓ in morphine demand dose. Zofran is second method for PBP. Other methods (cooling of wound, antihistamines, local anesthetics, topical doxepin, colloidal oatmeal, capsaicin, laser treatment, dapsone, unna boot, compression garments, & TENS) → ↓ PBP

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
5	Baker et al. (2001)	Setting not stated/ 17 pts w/ 10-60yrs of age	Double blind, Crossover trial/ 16days	Partial thickness & any % of TBSA. Not specified in description of wound healing stage	VAS	Combination of H1 receptor antagonist (cetirizine) & H2 receptor antagonist (cimetidine) is more effective in decreasing PBP than H1 receptor antagonist (diphenhydramine) during the first stage of treatment. It is more effective to treat PBP w/ scheduled medication than w/ as needed medication
6	Bell & Gabriel (2009)	Varied/ 10 trials - 9 Class II & 1 Class III.	Literature review (1950 – 2009) / Varied	Burn associated wound w/ pruritus. Not specified in the stage of wound	VAS	All PBP- Moisturizing cream, massage 10% TBSA or less- antihistamine, colloidal oatmeal w/ liquid paraffin, topical antihistamine, silicone gel sheeting More than 10% TBSA- oral non selective antihistamine, oral selective antihistamine, oral gabapentin
7	Brooks, Malic, & Judkins, (2008)	Varied/ Not specific in the number of articles	Literature review / Varied	Not specified in the stage of healing	Not stated	Algorithm consisting of 4 steps of treatment suggested. 1 st - oral antihistamine, topical emollient, 2 nd – clinical psychologist, 3 rd – massage, silicone sheeting, hypnosis, TENS, unna boot, topical nanocrystalline silver, capsaicin, 4 th – 8topical antihistamines, H1&H2 antagonists, topical steroid, doxepin, EMLA, gabapentin, dothiepin cream
8	Brooks, Phang, & Moazzam, (2007)	Inpatient & outpatient settings/ 5 cases	Case study/ 2 weeks	TBSA range 7-65% w/ unhealed burn wound	VAS	2weeks of Acticoat (Nanocrystalline silver) application is effective in PBP.
9	Campanati et al.	Unclear setting/ 30 pts	Non-RCT / 12 weeks	2 nd degree burns in healing stage	Not stated	Ozonated oil & hyaluronic acid have the same effect in reducing PBP 12 weeks of topical

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
	(2013)					application. Ozonated oil is more effective than hyaluronic acid in preventing post hyperpigmentation.
10	Cho et al. (2014)	Rehabilitation hospital setting/ 146 pts w/ hypertrophic scars	RCT/ Average 34.69days	All healed burn wound (scar)	VAS	Massage therapy is effective in improving pain, pruritus, & scar characteristics in hypertrophic scars after burn.
11	Farahani, Hekmatpou, & Khani (2013)	Inpatient setting/ 110 hospitalized pts	Quasi-experimental study / 1 month	2 nd degree burn wounds Stage of wound healing not clear-possibly not healed wound considering population	VAS	Twenty-minute Benson muscle relaxation is effective in relieving PBP.
12	Field et al. (2000)	Rehabilitation outpatient burn center/ 20 pts w/ PBP	RCT / 5 weeks	Healed burn wound	VAS	Massage therapy significantly decreased itching, pain, depression & anxiety in PB population w/ severe itching (30 min x 2days per week x 5weeks)
13	Gaida et al. (2003)	Outpatient setting/ 19 burn pts w/ scars	Pretest-posttest design / 8 weeks	Healed burn wound (scar)	VAS	LLLT demonstrated improvement in pain & pruritus among all participants.
14	Goutos (2013)	Varied/ The number of literature not stated	Literature review/ Varied	All stages of healing in burn wound	VAS / Itch Man Scale	Aggressive antihistamine is effective in the early phase, but less effective in the later stage of wounds. Gabapentin is persistent in decreasing PBP. Ondansetron-more effective than antihistamine. Serotonin- antihistamine effect TENS-effective in remodeling phase

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
15	Goutos, Dziewulski, & Richardson (2009)	Varied/ The number of literature not stated	Literature review/ Varied	Varied by methods of decreasing PBP	VAS	Peripheral & central aspects of pathway need to be included in decreasing PBP. Peripheral - cooling of the wound, antihistamines, topical Doxepin, local anesthetics, colloidal oatmeal, Laser tx, Aloe Vera, topical Dapsone, Unna boot, Compression garments, Ondansteron. Central - Gabapentin, TENS, Massage therapy, Psychological support
16	Goutos, Eldardiri, Khan, Dziewulski, & Richardson (2010)	Inpatient setting/ 91 burn pts (50-1 st part of the study, 41-2 nd part of the study)	Cohort, observational studies/ Intervention time not specified	Partial to full thickness burn injury. Healing stages not specified.	VAS / Itch Man Scale	Monotherapy in PBP: gabapentin monotherapy has more effective than chlorpheniramine. Polytherapy in PBP: Combination of gabapentin, cetirizine, & cyproheptadine is more effective than combination of 3 antihistamines (chlorpheniramine, hydroxyzine, & cyproheptadine)
17	Gurol, Polat, & Akcay (2010)	Inpatient setting/ 63 adolescent burn pts	Experimental study/ 5 weeks	2 nd to 3 rd degree burn wound. Healing stage not specified.	VAS	15minute massage twice per week for 5weeks applied to healthy skin around the wounds & surface of wound decreased PBP in adolescent population.
18	Hettrick (2004)	Outpatient clinic/ 20 pts w/ aged 18 to 75 yrs	RCT (Pilot study) / 3 weeks	2 nd to 3 rd degree recently healed burn wound	VAS	TENS significantly reduced PBP in the target population.
19	Hultman, Edkins, Wu, Calvert,	Outpatient eugical center/ 147 burn pts w/ hypertrophic burn scars	Cohort study/ 6 months	All healed burn wounds	VAS	Laser therapy decreased pain, pruritus, pliability, & paresthesia in population with hypertrophic burn scars

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
	& Cairns (2013)					
20	Jung et al. (2009)	Inpatient rehabilitation / 19 pts treated for burn injury	Retrospective, experimental study/ 2weeks	Healed burn wounds	VAS	With Naltrexone therapy, 14 pts reported improvement in experience of itching & 5 pts reported no change in itching.
21	La Salle, Rachel-ska, & Nedelec (2007)	Inpatient & outpatient settings/ 13 burn pts aged of 19-78	Experimental study/ 2weeks	TBSA of 7-70% & all grafted burn areas. Healing stages not specified	VAS	Participants stated satisfaction with Naltrexone in decreasing PBP & improved regarding frequency & duration of itching.
22	Lewis et al. (2012)	Inpatient setting / 52 burn pts, mean age of 35	RCT, Pilot study / 24 hours	Mean TBSA:7.2%, mostly partial thickness burn wound & newly healed scar	VAS	Medilixir is more effective to minimize PBP than aqueous cream.
23	(Li-Sang et al., 2006)	Outpatient clinic/ 45 burn pts	RCT / 6 months	Post traumatic hypertrophic scars	VAS	SGS was effective to reduce thickness, pain, itchiness, & pliability of the severe hypertrophic scar.
24	(Li-Tsang, Zheng, & Lau, 2010)	Routine life (participant's routine area) / 104 burn pts	RCT / 6 months	Burn scars	VAS	SGS showed more effective in decreasing pain and pruritus than the scar thickness. CTG & PG group showed significant improvement in scar thickness after 6 months of intervention (CTG>PG).
25	Mendham (2004)	Inpatient setting / 35 pediatric	Experimental study/ 4weeks –	Burn wounds and skin loss from meningitis. Not healed wound	Not stated	Gabapentin reduced itching in healing wound & decreased antihistamine intake in pediatric population.

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
		wound pts	18months			
26	Nedelec, Rachel-ska, Parnell, & La Salle (2012)	Not clear / 18 pts having PBP treated in the hospital	RCT, Pilot study / 4 weeks	All healed burn wounds (scars)	Yosipovitch's questionnaire	Provase decreased PBP in weekly frequency, daily episode of itch, & duration of itch episode.
27	Ogawa & Hyaku-soku (2008)	Inpatient setting/ 14 pts w/ hypertrophic scars from burns	Prospective, Cohort study / 2 months	All healed burn wounds (scars)	VAS	Mugwort lotion is effective for improving itching & sleep disturbance. (Two months of Mugwort treatment decreased symptoms)
28	(Otene & Onuma-egbu, 2013)	Not clear / 35 plastic surgeons	Descriptive study / varied	All burn wounds	No tool used	PBP relief methods used by % of plastic surgeons - 57.1 (oral meds), 22.9 (Injections), 8.6 (topical agents), 5.7 (reassure pts), 5.7 (combination of oral & topical agents). 85.7 without anti-pruritus protocol.
29	Pfab et al. (2013)	Not specific / Non applicable	Literature review / 5 weeks	Any skin conditions that caused itching	Not stated	15 minute massage therapy twice a week over 5weeks reduced itching, pain, & anxiety levels in burn adolescents.
30	Ratcliff et al. (2005)	Inpatient setting / 286 burn children	Retrospective chart review / Varied	All burn wounds : Various wound stages	Itch Man Scale	Itching management protocol for children; 1)Moisturizing body shampoo & lotions, topical ointments (not hydrocortisone creams) 2)Diphenhydramine 1.25mg/kg/dose po Q 6h 3)If itch remains poorly controlled, subsequently add hydroxyzine 0.6mg/kg/dose q 6h, then cyproheptadine 0.1mg/kg/dose po q6h so that one of the medications is given q2hrs

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
31	Richardson, Upton, & Rippon (2014)	Varied / Literature up to 2013	Literature review / Varied	Four different stages of healing in burn wounds	Not stated	PBP management algorithm per 4 healing phases of wound suggested – inflammatory phase, inflammatory/proliferative phase, proliferative/remodeling phase, & remodeling phase.
32	Roh et al. (2007)	Outpatient clinic/ 35 burn pts	Pretest – posttest / 3 months	Burn scars from partial or full thickness burns on forearm or hand	Itch man Scale	PBP significantly decreased by SRMT in burn victims with scars from partial to full thickness on the forearm or hand.
33	Rowley-Conwy (2014)	Varied / The number of literature not stated	Double-blind peer review/ varied	All stages of burn wound	Not stated	PBP is reduced with massage w/ emollient cream, cool baths, pressure garments, & oral and topical antihistamines & analgesics.
34	Upton, Penn, Richardson, & Rippon (2014)	Varied / 12 articles published between 1980-2013	Narrative review/ Varied	Any skin conditions causing pruritus- atopic dermatitis, burn wounds, skin disorders, pruritic skin disease	Not stated	Five psychological approaches to treat wound associated itching are suggested. (Habit reversal, Suggestions, Relaxation training, Massage, & Itch-coping programs)
35	Waked, Nagib, & Ashm (2013)	Inpatient setting / 40 burn pts	RCT/ 1 month	2 nd & 3 rd degree burn wounds, 10-15% TBSA. – All Healed scars	5-D Itch scale	Triamcinolone acetone phonophoresis is as useful as TENS to reduce PBP
36	Warner, Coffee, & Yowler (2014)	Varied / Number of articles not specified	Review / Varied	All phases of burn wounds	Not stated	Early pruritus management: H-1 receptor blocker (cetirizine) on as scheduled basis not as needed basis combined with frequent massage of moisturizers. Neuro-inflammatory transmitter blockers (gabapentin & pregabalin) is effective because itch-specific neurons won't be stimulated by

No	Authors (year)	Setting/ Participants	Study Design / Intervention Time	Characteristics of Burn Wound	Itching assessment Tool	Study Result
						using this medicine.
37	Whitaker (2001)	Inpatient setting / One case (19yrs old)	Case study / 2 weeks	Healed 70% TBSA flame burn wound (scar)	VAS	2 weeks of TENS is effective in decreasing PBP. Day #1: 62.5% decreased in itching within 4hrs of application. Day #2: 88% decreased within 4hrs of application. Day #3: No itching within 4hrs of application.
38	Zachariah et al. (2011)	Varied / Number of literature not specified	Review / Varied	All burn wounds. Healing stage not specified	VAS	Current tx options for PBP summarized; Antihistamines (H1 & H2 receptor antagonists), Topical alternatives over the healed burn wounds (colloidal oatmeal baths, EMLA, corticosteroids, massage therapy, Doxepin cream). Adjuncts (Biofeedback therapy, psychological support, combined w/pharmacological agents, TENS), Newer medicine: Ondansetron (5HT-3 receptor antagonist), Gabapentin (anti-epileptic drug), Pregabalin (anti-convulsant), Paroxetine (SSRI), & Naltrexone (opioid antagonist)
<p><i>Notes.</i> CTG = combined pressure therapy and silicone gel sheeting group; EMLA = eutectic mixture of local anesthetic; h = hour; hrs = hours; H1 = histamine 1; H2 = histamine 2; LLLT = low level laser therapy; PBP = post burn pruritus; PG = pressure therapy group; pts = patients; RCT = randomized clinical trial; SGS = silicone gel sheeting; SRMT = skin rehabilitation massage therapy; SSRI = selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor; TBSA = total body surface area; TENS = transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation; VAS = visual analog scale.</p>						

PROJECT MANUSCRIPT

Thirty-eight articles were reviewed. Eighteen articles identified pharmacological effects on post burn pruritus that included single medicine use and two or three combined medicine. Effective pharmacological, both oral and topical, methods used in decreasing pruritus were antihistamines, Pregabalin, analgesics, corticosteroids, Gabapentin, Naltrexone, Botox, Provase, Capsaicin, colloidal oatmeal, Aloe Vera, topical Dapsone, Doxepin, Mugwort lotion, EMLA, Ozonated oil, and hyaluronic acid. Fifteen of the thirty eight articles stated positive non-pharmacological methods in relieving post burn pruritus. Examples of effective non-pharmacological methods included: cool bath, massage therapy, laser therapy, TENS, TAP, muscle relaxation, psychological approach, biofeedback therapy, silicone gel sheeting, Acticoat®, and pressure garment therapy. Of the studies, five supported combination of pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods to reduce post burn pruritus.

The outcome of the systemic literature review regarding pruritus relief in post burn populations was synthesized and evaluated based on best outcomes which are pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions. Accordingly, an advanced practice nurse (APN) driven post burn pruritus relief protocol was developed (Figure 4). This protocol was designed to apply to three different stages of wound healing such as: pre-healing (no granulation tissue); healing (partly granulated tissue); and healed stages (scar formation); and, recommended dosages per each intervention (Table2). Non-pharmacology interventions are recommended before pharmacological interventions based on established effectiveness.

Figure 4. Post Burn Pruritus Relief Protocol.

Table 2

Post Burn Pruritus Relief Protocol Guideline (Recommended Dosage)

Wound Stage	Treatment Plan	Recommended Dosage (refer to article No. in Table 1)
Pre-healing stage	Massage therapy to intact skin	15 minutes/day, 2 days/week, 5 weeks or as needed. (17, 29)
	Benson Muscle Relaxation therapy	20 minutes daily for 1 month or as needed (11)
	Pharmacological treatment - Pregabalin alone - Pregabalin & two antihistamines - Gabapentin alone - Gabapentin & H1 blocker - Gabapentin & two H1 blockers - Combination of H1 & H2 blockers	(1, 2, 5, 6, 16, 25) - 150-300mg/day (divided by 2 or 3 times) - Pregabalin (same dose), Cetirizine 10-20mg/day (one or twice a day), & Pheniramine 25mg/day before sleep - 300-900mg/day (adult), 5-10mg/kg/day (child) - Gabapentin (same dose) & Cetirizine 10-20mg/day - Gabapentin & Cetirizine (same doses) & Cyproheptadine 4mg every 6hours - Cetirizine: 20mg/day (adult) & 10mg/day (pediatric patient), & Cimetidine: 1200mg/day, divided by 4 (adult), 30mg/kg/day, divided by 4 (child)
	Naltrexone (supplemental pharmacological treatment)	25-50mg/day before sleep for 2weeks (20, 21)
	All treatments for pre-healing stage & Topical agents (Ozonated oil or Hyaluronic acid gel 0.2%)	Ozonated oil 2drops/cm ² once a day or Hyaluronic acid gel ½ finger tip/cm ² daily For 12 weeks or as needed (9)
Healed stage	Benson muscle relaxation	Same dose as above (11)
	Massage therapy applied to healed wound	15-30minutes, 1-3times/week for 5-12weeks (10, 12, 29, 32)
	Acticoat®	Apply for 2weeks (8)
	LLLTT or regular Laser Therapy	LLLTT: 2 times/week for 8weeks (13) Regular laser therapy: once per month for 6 month (19)
	TENS	Once a day for 2-3weeks (14, 18, 37)
	TAP	3 times/week for 1 month (35)
	Silicone Gel Sheeting	Wear 12-24hours/day for 6 months (8, 23, 24)
	Unna boot®	Apply as needed (7, 15)
	Topical agents - Medilixir® - Mugwort lotion - Provase® - Ozonated oil - Hyaluronic acid gel 0.2%	- Once a day for 2 weeks (22) - 2 times/day for 2 months (27) - 3 times/day for 4 weeks (26) - 2drops/cm ² once a day (9) - ½finger tip/cm ² daily (9)
	Moisturizing body shampoo	Use as needed (30)
Capsaicin cream	Apply as needed (7)	

Each stage of wound healing can be managed by both non-pharmacological and pharmacological interventions. Non-pharmacological methods are less invasive interventions and are considered the primary intervention. On the other hand, Pharmacological methods are more invasive interventions and are most times used as a supplement to potentiate the effect of non-pharmacological interventions or to decrease possible adverse effects of combination medications.

Non-pharmacological interventions are versatile and can be combined with any other non-pharmacological interventions as well as pharmacological interventions. Choice for non-pharmacological interventions will be considered by the facility's resources and patients' preferences. However, only one option from pharmacological interventions should be used with any non-pharmacological interventions only when non-pharmacological methods are not effective. Also, single medicine can be started when adding pharmacological methods. For example, in pre-healing stage, they can use all of non-pharmacological methods (both massage and Benson muscle relaxation therapy) and only one of pharmacological methods (either Pregabalin alone, Pregabalin & two antihistamines, Gabapentin alone, Gabapentin & H1 blocker, or Gabapentin & two H1 blockers, or Combination of H1 & H2 blockers). In this case, only Pregabalin needs to be initiated, but if Pregabalin alone does not effectively relieve pruritus two antihistamines can be added (Figure 4). Moreover, if pruritus persists regardless of interventions used, the following medications can be added to reduce symptoms: Zofran® (ondansetron), Serotonin, SSRI (selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor: Paroxetine), Doxepin® (tricyclic antidepressant), Gabapentin, Naltrexone, Topical Antihistamines, Topical Steroid, EMLA® Cream (lidocaine 2.5% & prilocaine 2.5%),

Dothiepin (Tricyclic agent) cream, and Botox® (botulinum toxin). This post burn pruritus relief protocol was developed after a comprehensive systematic review of the literature with best practices identified. APNs can also use this evidence based protocol as standardized procedure for prescriptive authority.

DISCUSSION

This protocol, the second of any post burn pruritus protocols is the first APN driven evidence based protocol that uses non-pharmacological interventions as a primary method of choice to reduce post burn pruritus. This protocol can be implemented in practice by APNs or RNs depending on the choice of interventions used. In addition, this protocol has recommended dosage and period for each intervention to clearly guide APNs and RNs. Using the Rosswurm and Larrabee model the nurse in clinical practice can assess the efficacy of this post burn pruritus protocol to ascertain if the protocol: 1) relieved discomfort from pruritus; 2) lessened disturbances on daily life that can include low concentration, agitation, anxiety, and a flat affect; 3) and increased quality of life. The 5-D Itch Scale (Appendix A) and/or the Visual Analogue Scale (Appendix B) are both valid and reliable and can be used before and then after the treatment method to quantify patient outcomes. The results from this systematic literature review and the model for implementing practice change, significantly contribute to the treatment of post burn pruritus. Non-pharmacological and Pharmacological interventions for post burn pruritus have been identified and presented in an easily identified protocol to improve patient outcomes and clinical practice.

The findings of this systematic literature review and proposed protocol will help to advance the DNP role in research and translational inquiry. This protocol will be utilized in the future to develop interventional studies to enhance post burn pruritus management as well as to relieve patient suffering.

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APPENDIX A

5 –D ITCH SCALE

(Adapted from Elman, Hyman, Gabriel, & Mayo, 2010)

1. **Duration:** During the last 2 weeks, how many hours a day have you been itching?
- | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| Less than 6hrs/day | 6-12 hrs/day | 12-18 hrs/day | 18-23 hrs/day | All day |
| <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
2. **Degree:** Please rate the intensity of your itching over the past 2 weeks
- | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| Not present | Mild | Moderate | Severe | Unbearable |
| <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
3. **Direction:** Over the past 2 weeks has your itching gotten better or worse compared to the previous month?
- | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------------|--------------------------------------|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| Completely resolved | Much better, but still present | Little bit better, but still present | Unchanged | Getting worse |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
4. **Disability:** Rate the impact of your itching on the following activities over the last 2 weeks
- | | | | | | | |
|--------------------------|--------------------------|------------------------------------|----------------------------------|---|---|------------------------------|
| | Never affects sleep | Occasionally delays falling asleep | Frequently delays falling asleep | Delays falling asleep and occasionally wakes me up at night | Delays falling asleep and frequently wakes me up at night | |
| Sleep | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | |
| | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 | |
| | N/A | Never affects this activity | Rarely affects this activity | Occasionally affects this activity | Frequently affects this activity | Always affects this activity |
| Leisure/Social | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| | | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| Housework/Errands | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| | | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| Work/School | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| | | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
5. **Distribution:** Mark whether itching has been present in the following parts of your body over the last 2 weeks. If a body part is not listed, choose the one that is closest anatomically.
- | | |
|--|--|
| Head/Scalp <input type="checkbox"/> Present
Face <input type="checkbox"/>
Chest <input type="checkbox"/>
Abdomen <input type="checkbox"/>
Back <input type="checkbox"/>
Buttocks <input type="checkbox"/>
Thighs <input type="checkbox"/>
Lower legs <input type="checkbox"/>
Tops of Feet/Toes <input type="checkbox"/> | Soles <input type="checkbox"/> Present
Palms <input type="checkbox"/>
Tops of Hands/Fingers <input type="checkbox"/>
Forearms <input type="checkbox"/>
Upper Arms <input type="checkbox"/>
Points of Contact w/ Clothing (e.g waistband, undergarment) <input type="checkbox"/>
Groin <input type="checkbox"/> |
|--|--|

APPENDIX B**VISUAL ANALOGUE SCALE**

(Adapted from Elman et al., 2010)

Example:

APPENDIX C**ITCH MAN SCALE**

(Adapted from Morris et al., 2012)

0
Comfortable,
no itch

1
Itches a little;
does not interfere
with activity

2
Itches more;
sometimes
interferes
with activity

3
Itches a lot;
difficult to be
still, concentrate

4
Itches most terribly;
impossible to sit
still, concentrate

APPENDIX D

TABLE OF EVIDENCE FOR PROPOSAL

Summary of Studies Including Pruritus in Burn Patients

(Author(s), year), Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
(Ahuja & Gupta, 2012) To compare the use of pregabalin to other methods in managing PB pruritus	Double blind, RCT Key variables: PB pruritus, Itch, Pregabalin Gabapentin	80 adult outpatients from the department of Burns & Plastic Surgery of Lok Nayak Hospital, New Delhi from 04/2010 to 01/2011 IC: Age 18-60yrs, TBSA > 5%, Predominantly 2 nd degree burns, & wound either in healing (80% epithelialized) or healed < 3month back EC: Co-morbid conditions	4 groups divided from A to D. They were asked at 3, 7, 14, 21, 28 days after tx regarding VAS scores All groups received massage A: Antihistamine (cetirizine + pheniramine) use B: Combination of antihistamine & pregabalin C: Placebo (Vitamin B) use D: Pregabalin use A: Cetirizine + Pheniramine 10mg QD or bid + 25mg HS B: Pregabalin + Cetirizine + Pheniramine 75 mg bid, tid, or 150mg bid + 10mg QD or bid + 25mg HS C: Vitamin B 1 capsule QD, bid or 2 capsules bid D: Pregabalin 75mg bid,	<u>For mild itching pts (VAS 2-5):</u> B & D group showed 77.5% & 23.3% of remission of itching, respectively on 3days after tx B & D group showed 100% & 96.7% of remission of itching, respectively on 28days after tx <u>For moderate itching pts (VAS 6-8):</u> B & D group showed 64.8% & 61.4% of remission of itching, respectively on 3days after tx B & D group showed 92.6% & 92.8% of remission of itching, respectively on 28days after tx <u>For severe itching pts (VAS: 9-10):</u> B & D group showed 56.9% & 52.7% of remission of itching, respectively on 3days after tx. Both B & D group showed 78.9% of remission of itching on 28days after tx.	Pregabalin alone & combined antihistamine w/pregabalin showed significant effect in decreasing itching Addition of antihistamines does not seem to be beneficial to decrease pruritus Also, massage therapy itself showed effectiveness within 2-4wks after tx that showed it can be used as adjunctive tx Limits: the study did not define end point of anti-pruritic therapy

(Author(s), year), Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
(Ahuja, Gupta, Gupta, & Shrivastava, 2010) Evaluating the effect of gabapentin tx compared to the combination of gabapentin and cetirizine tx in PB pruritus	Single site, prospective & randomized controlled study IV: gabapentin, cetirizine, combination of gabapentin & cetirizine. DV: itch, PB pruritus	Randomly selected 20 PB patients per each group of gabapentin tx, cetirizine tx, & both tx Department of Burns at Lok Nayak Hospital (07/2009-10/2009) IC:12–70yrs old, burn area > 5% tbsa, predominantly 2nd degree burns, > 80% wounds epithelialized or healed completely < 1 month back	GA – cetirizine tx only GB – gabapentin tx only GC – gabapentin & cetirizine VAS used for antipruritic effect at baseline, 3, 7, 14, 21, & 28days after tx for each G Different drug dose used based on the VAS (2-5, 6-8, 9-10)	GA: pruritus reduction in 52% GB: pruritus reduction in 95% GC: pruritus reduction in 94% Onset of action with gabapentin significantly faster than the cetirizine: 32% in GA vs 74% in GB on the 3rd day of the treatment	Combination of centrally acting drugs & peripherally acting drugs did not show better effect in reducing PB pruritus compared to using centrally acting drugs (gabapentin) Limitations: Need for larger sample size to generalize, > 1% graft were excluded, Limited period of data collection, Single site study Note: the study suggested PB pruritus relief protocol and the proper dose of gabapentin in the future
(Akhtar & Brooks, 2012) To see the	Prospective, experimental study	10 pts who failed in managing PB pruritus w/ conventional	During the study, only 8 pts included due to 2 pts excluded for language barrier & not a burn scar.	All 8pts stated severe itching before tx – 2pts10/10, 1 pt-9/10, 4 pts-8/10, 1pt-6/10.	Botox can successfully be used to treat PB pruritus that is resistant to conventional

(Author(s), year), Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
effect of botulinum toxin (botox) as a new agent in managing PB pruritus	Key variables: Botulinum, toxin, burns, itching	therapies (silicone gel tx, compression garments, massage tx). 1pt (kid) excluded. :11.3 months f/u period. 2-3 rd degree burns All scarred areas	F/u done before tx, 1wk, 2wks after tx and b/w3-23months after tx. VAS used to assess itching degree.	All 8 pts described symptoms as "0" out of 10 at 2wks after tx Three pts labeled the score as 1, 2, & 3 at 6, 4, & 3 months after tx 5 others had no itching since 2wks after tx	therapies
(Anand, 2012) To show the effectiveness of gabapentin for pruritus in palliative care	Literature review Key variables: gabapentin, pruritus, palliative care, hospice, pain	Reviewed studies regarding use of gabapentin for pruritus (cause, mechanism, mgt & classification of pruritus)	Classification of pruritus: peripheral (prurioreceptive), central (neuropathic, neurogenic, & psychogenic) Causes of pruritus: uremic, cancer (solid tumors or hematologic), opioid-induced, cholestasis, brachioradial, burns r/t itch	Gabapentin is safe & effective in uremic pruritus, cancer/hematologic causes, opioid-induced itch, brachioradial pruritus, burns pruritus, & pruritus of unknown origin Recommended doses: Uremic pruritus-100mg after each HD, Opioid-induced itch-1200mg before spinal anesthesia w/morphine use	Well-designed placebo-controlled randomized trials are needed to show the effectiveness of gabapentin in pruritus not responsive to other modalities of tx
(Baker et al., 2001) To identify association in managing PB pruritus by using oral & topical	Double blind, crossover trial Key variables: H1 antagonist, H2 antagonist,	Started w/32 pts, but 17pts completed the study 4 groups w/ 2 different tx combination & 4 different period	A1: Cetirizine + Cimetidine A2: placebo + Diphenhydramine B1: Revive lotion B2: Corrective concepts Each group had 4tx options (A1B1, A1B2, A2B1, A2B2) in different time frame of 1-4, 5-8, 9-12, &	During days 1-16, no significant differences b/w A1 (A1B1, A1B2) & A2 (A2B1, A2B2) even with some improvement in both tx During days 1-4, A1 had significant improvement compared to A2 During days 5-16, no significant	Use as scheduled meds instead of prn meds to be effective

(Author(s), year), Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
medications			13-16th day Pts completed itch score (VAS) before tx, at 1, 6, & 12hr intervals after tx	differences b/w A1 & A2 possibly from the residual effect of previously used tx Also, no difference b/w B1 & B2 noted.	
(Bell & Gabriel, 2009) To do evidence based review on the tx of PB pruritus	Literature review via Ovid Medline b/w 1950 & 2009 Key variables: Pruritus, itching, burns	10 trials reviewed & accepted. : 9 Class II & 1 Class III.	Class II: studies where certainly reliable data are collected (observational studies, cohort studies, prevalence studies & case-control studies) Class III: evidence provided by clinical series, comparative studies, case reviews, case reports, & expert opinion The classified literature was determined to support guideline status as outlined by the Practice Guideline for Burn care 2006 VAS used for itching	Pharmacologic methods (w/ specific dose) below decreased PB pruritus significantly; Selective antihistamine antagonists (cetirizine/cimetidine) in adult & pediatric population, Atarax in adult population, Gabapentin in pediatric population, Colloidal Oatmeal (topical) in adults, & EMLA (topical) in pediatric population Non-pharmacologic methods decreased PB pruritus significantly; Pulsed dye laser in adult & pediatric pts, Silicone gel sheeting in adult & pediatric pts, Massage in adult population, & TENS in adult population	The study suggested tx plan according to TBSA To all PB pruritus; Moisturizing cream, Specified b/w TBSA <10% & >10%
(Brooks, Malic, & Judkins, 2008) To review current knowledge of	Literature review Key variables: Itch, Burns, Nerve			Current standard tx: oral antihistamines & emollients Literature evidence on PB pruritus tx: 1. Combination of colloidal oatmeal & paraffin bath emollient + antihistamines 2. Combination of different antihistamines 3. Combination of H1	

(Author(s), year), Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
pruritus pathologic processes & anti-itch tx, & offer algorithm to decrease PB itching	transmission, receptor agonists, Anti-itch therapy			&H2 antagonists 4.Gabapentin use 5.TENS, massage tx, Laser tx, Unna boot, Doxepin cream, EMLA cream, silicone gel sheets, Acticoat dressing. Algorithm for PB pruritus management suggested w/ 4 steps	
(Brooks, Phang, & Moazzam, 2007) To report the effect of Acticoat (Nanocrystalline silver) for itch relief in the burn patients	Case study Key variables: Nanocrystalline silver, Itch, burn	5 subjects w/ 7, 20, 40, 45, & 65% of TBSA having mixed-thickness burns from both inpatient & outpatient clinic	Acticoat applied for 2 wks and the intervals from original injury to application were 2, 3, 3, 6, & 8 months Before & after 2 wks of application, VAS assessed and compared	VAS score: 7.4 before tx decreased to 3.1 after tx ($p = 0.0022$). Ex) Pt w/ excoriation of the skin due to itching showed absence of excoriation following acticoat tx	Limit: This report did not indicate the condition of wounds whether they were healed or unhealed. However, it is assumed they were unhealed or in the healing process because acticoat is used for unhealed wounds in current practice
(Campanati et al., 2013) To evaluate the clinical effect of the topical application of ozonated oil on second degree	Prospective, comparative, single-blind, non-randomized and controlled clinical trial. Key variables:	30 pts w/partial to full thickness 2 nd degree burns treated b/w 06/2011 & 01/2012 IC: before the stage of re-	Pts applied ozonated oil on half of the burn lesion and hyaluronic acid on the other half of the lesion once a day for 12wks Clinical features of each lesion (erythema, tension,	Ozonated oil had the same efficacy of hyaluronic acid in reducing symptoms r/t burns (erythema, tension, height, itching & burning sensation) after 12 wks of topical application Ozonated oil was more effective than hyaluronic acid in preventing post-lesional hyperpigmentation	Limit: lack of a histological comparison b/w two agents

(Author(s), year), Purpose	Design & Key Variables	Sample & Setting	Measurements, Operational Definitions of Variables	Results or Findings	Conclusions, Study Limitations, & Notes
skin burns comparing with the treatment w/ hyaluronic acid gel	ozonated oil, hyaluronic acid, symptoms r/t burns, post-lesional hyperpigmentation	epithelisation EC: keloids, hypertrophic scars, photo type > III, allergy or intolerance to the topical agents, DM, CTD, thyroid diseases, CVD, or tx of corticosteroid or vasodilators	height, itching & burning sensation) assessed w/ IVCP at baseline, 6months & 12 months after tx. Pts completed survey focusing on “what part of the treated lesion had improves more?”, which topical tx is more comfortable?”, & “what tx do you prefer?”		
(Carrougher et al., 2013) Investigating PB pruritus via self-report	Multisite prospective longitudinal study Key variables: PB pruritus, related distress, PB pain, sleeping difficulty, wound conditions	Burn patient age 18 & older from burn research study (N = 930). G1(N = 637): patients injured b/w 2006 & 2010. –no more than 2yrs PB injury G2(N = 336): completed 2 yr f/u before & provided 5 or 10 yr f/u –over 5yrs PB injury. Setting: in the	G1(w/in 24months PB injury) Questionnaire for burn r/t pruritus provided at D/C, 6, 12 & 24 months PB G2 (over 2yrs PB injury): 2-yr f/u & long-term f/u in 5yrs (172subjects) & in 10yrs (164subjects) PB injury 43 out of 930subjects in common to both G1 & G2 Group 2 (LTF) – f/u at 5 & 10 yrs after burn injury & 43 subjects completed from	More than 73% of adult burn survivors suffered from pruritus episodes during the first 2 yrs following injury; In 75.7% of long-term burn survivors, pruritus existed <6hrs/ day from mild to moderate for the intensity; In more than ½ of long-term burn survivor, pruritus still impacted their leisure, household, vocational activities & sleeping; Predictors of PB pruritus include female gender, younger age, %TBSA-burn, depth of injury, %TBSA grafted, dry skin, & thick or raised scars;	Limitations- Variances b/w responses regarding wound condition d/t self-report based data & no P/E information; Limited control ability for question variability & question confusion d/t various data collection methods; No current tx method for PB attained; Future study needed to assess tx methods for PB pruritus

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		care facility at D/C & thereafter via mail to complete the survey	D/C to 2yr f/u	No differences in PB pruritus noted regarding ethnicity/race, scar discoloration, & open/closed wounds	Note: Since the data collection method was self-report only, experts' objective data, especially for wounds are needed
(Casaer, Kums, Wouters, Van den kerckhove, & Van den Berghe, 2008) Exploring pruritus prevalence & precipitating factors in small burns & effects on daily life	Non-experimental, Retrospective, & observational study IVs: %TBSA-burn, nature of burn wounds, tx received, wound healing, pruritus tx DV: Characteristic of pruritus	268 post burn patients treated in the university of Leuven Outpatient Burn Injury Clinic in 2004 A relative who lived in the same house answered for a pt w/ disability or language problems	Questionnaire was made in Dutch w/ collaboration of a burn surgeon, a child psychiatrist, a registered nurse, a specialized physiotherapist & an intensive care physician (no detail info on the questionnaire noted)	No difference in time b/w injury & interview in patients reporting pruritus & no pruritus ($P = 0.3$); Similar pruritus incidence obtained from patients or a relative ($P = 0.2$) Pruritus incidence 50%; ¼ of the moderate pruritus group had negative impact on daily life ($P = .0002$) & sleep pattern ($P = .002$) Patients had less pruritus when the age at burn injury was < than 2yrs, %TBSA-burn was < 2%, & wound healing was < 3 weeks, but more pruritus when the burn areas were trunk or lower limbs ($P < 0.001$) Age < 50yrs & %TBSA-burn had expectation for severe pruritus in MVLr analysis Half of patient having pruritus received treatment & 25% of them reported distinct effect; No association b/w wearing of garments & application of	First study on pruritus in a large population w/small burns (TBSA 2%) Limits: High P values for the info obtained methods & the time b/w injury & interview; Questionnaire is not psychometrically validated, not age adapted, & not specified in races, opioid intake & burn wound traits Notes: Further studies needed for impact on QoL, development of pathologic scarring, early consultation in the plastic surgery clinic, a formal referral to general practitioner f/u,

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(Cho et al., 2014) To evaluate the effect of burn rehabilitation massage therapy on hypertrophic scar after burn	Prospective RCT Key variables: burn, hypertrophic scars, Rehabilitation , Massage therapy	Sample size: 146 pts w/hypertrophic scars after acute burn care (EG:76, CG:70) CG-received ROM exercise & standard therapy EG-added Burn rehabilitation massage therapy in addition to the therapies CG received	Before & after massage therapy, EG & CG assessed & compared for pain(VAS), Pruritus, & Scar characteristics (thickness, melanin, erythema, TEWL, sebum, elasticity) b/w 2 groups Measurement tools: Thickness, melanin & erythema, TEWL, sebum, & elasticity assessed by USG, Mexameter, Tewameter, Sebumeter, & Cutometer, respectively Burn rehabilitation massage therapy given 30min a day for 3times a week, average 12.5 times by specialized burn rehabilitation massage therapists	silicones noted No significant differences b/w EG & CG for gender, age, TBSA, interval b/w burn injury & rehabilitation therapy, period of rehabilitation therapy, VAS, pruritus, & scar characteristics before treatment Results after burn rehabilitation massage therapy; EG showed significant improvement in pain, itching, scar thickness (↓thickness), melanin (↓melanin), erythema (↓erythema), scar TEWL (↓TEWL), & sebum (↑sebum) However, for scar elasticity, EG showed significant improvement only in immediate distension & gross skin elasticity	& a preventive tx Burn massage therapy is effective in improving pain, pruritus, & scar characteristics in hypertrophic scars after burn Limits: Massage given only for short period (average: 34.7days), so long-term effects not identified. Evolution of hypertrophic scar not considered → Future study regarding comparison of the effect of massage on new & old burn scars
(Farahanil, Hekmatpou, & Khani, 2013) Investigating the effect of muscle relaxation on	Quasi-experimental study IC: no mental diseases; older than 9 yrs; no skin	Convenient sampling, 110 hospitalized 2 nd degree burn pts, randomly allocated to case & control groups. (55 per each	Demographic info obtained. Pain VAS, Pruritus assessment scale, & v/s assessed before & after 20 min Benson relaxation method to control group. A month later, these 4 assessments performed	Muscle relaxation technique is effective in relieving the pain, pruritus & v/s of pts suffering from burns. Its use as a therapeutic & alleviative method to be suggested for patients suffering from burns	Limitations: No explanation for other methods to reduce pain or pruritus used or not No explanation of frequency of relaxation tx

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pain, pruritus & v/s among pts suffering from burns	disease, depression, diabetes, renal failure, & metabolic disorders	group: control & case group) Setting: Arak University hospital in Iran	before & after 20 min Benson verbal & muscle relaxation technique to case group Chi-square, independent t-test, paired t-test & Mann-Whitney test were used		
(Field et al., 2000) To evaluate the effect of massage therapy in reducing PB itching, pain, & psychological symptoms	RCT Key variables: Massage, PB itching, pain, anxiety, depression	20 pts w/ PB itching (EG:10, CG:10) Inclusion criteria: A closed, moderate sized wound & c/o severe itching	CG received standard medical care. EG received standard medical care & massage therapy on the wound for 30min, twice a week for 5wks. After massage therapy, Itching, pain, depression & anxiety compared b/w two groups. VAS used for itching assessment	There was significant reduction in itching, pain, depression & anxiety in EG	Massage therapy significantly decreased itching, pain, depression & anxiety in PB population w/ severe itching. Limits: needs larger sample & long term use of massage therapy studies
(Gaida et al., 2003) To evaluate the effects of low level laser therapy (LLLT) on scar, pain & pruritus in PB patients	Pretest posttest design Key variables: low level laser therapy, burn scar, VSS	19 burn pts (M14, F5, aged 18-77yrs) All pts suffered from burn scars before the study and none of them had received tx w/ corticosteroids, dermabrasion,	VSS (for ht, pliability, pigmentation & vascularity of scar), VAS (for pruritus & pain), digital photographs & macroscopic evaluation were performed before & after tx	17 out of 19 lesions showed macroscopic improvement while 2 lesions did not improve. :Scar < 12months improved better than scar > 12months LLLT demonstrated improvement in pain & pruritus among 19 PB population	Selecting other side of skin in the same pt is possible weakness of the study Need more studies that have higher number of sample and control site from different people rather than the same group w/ different sites

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		compression w/silicone or excision before LLLT In each pt, 1 burn scar was given by LLLT & 1 similar burn scar was defined as a control area(no tx)			
(Goutos, 2010) Current knowledge & management of pts with PB pruritus among physicians	Descriptive study. Key variables: Healing method, pruritus, burn depth, Oral pharmacological agents, Pruritus management	Plastic surgery specialists from 22 burn units in the UK (n = 22; one plastic surgeon represents each burn unit) Sample mean experience in burn care of 2.3yrs among subjects Period: January, 2008 – March, 2008	Phone questionnaire distributed to inquire burn relevant pruritus (12 questions in questionnaire) Variables: 1. % of burn patients affected by pruritus, 2. differences in adult & pediatric burn patients for pruritus, 3. assessment tool availability for pruritus in pt daily care plans, 4. diurnal variation of pruritus, 5. effect stage of healing & pruritus, 6. effect of burn depth &	The median of postburn pruritus is 80% (range: 5-100%) 21 burn units (95.45%) have no daily assessment on pruritus in a quantitative manner; 1 unit uses Itch Man Scale on a daily base; 12 units (54.55%) reported more intense pruritus in the evening; 34.36%, 34.09% & 20.45% felt more pruritus during the wound healing, remodeling & acute phase, respectively; 40.91% felt more pruritus in superficial partial thickness burns; 40.91% & 31.82% felt more pruritus in wounds treated w/ dressings & w/grfts, respectively; 90.91% used antihistamines as a 1 st line for pruritus; 1 unit used ondansetron, & 3 units used gabapentin alone or with an	The first study to explore the knowledge on burn pruritus among physicians, reporting a lack of consensus on many aspects; Protocols for burn pruritus needed; The reasons for lack of protocols include low consensus in physicians, low consideration of pt preferences, & poor resource allocation Limit: Low Sample size.

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			pruritus, healing method & pruritus, 7. 1 st & 2 nd pharmacological agents, other supplement in pruritus management, 8. protocols in postburn pruritus in the unit	antihistamine; 5 units used additional pruritic relief methods: 2 units utilized psychologists, other 2 units used massage therapy, & 1 used silicone products for pruritic wounds; Only one unit has a specified protocol for pruritus management	Notes: The study showed relevant research according to question contents & suggested more research on each content to relieve pruritus
(Goutos, 2013) To provide an update of the pathophysiology of PB itching by utilizing a comparative exploration of pruritus & pain mechanisms, as well as by integrating emerging anatomical, neurophysiological, & pharmacological data	Literature review Key variables: Burns, Pruritus, Pain mechanism, Pathophysiology.	Reviewed & summarized articles		PB Pruritus lasts longer than wound healing period (inflammatory, proliferative, & remodeling phase) Pruritus classification (by Twycross et al): Pruritoceptive, Neuropathic, Neurogenic, & Psychogenic pruritus) Aggressive antihistamine is effective in the early phase, but in the later stages wounds appear to be less effective to antihistamine therapy Evidence from the effectiveness of therapeutic approaches acting on the CNS: Gabapentin-persistent therapeutic effect of gabapentin is due to the ability of preventing CNS sensitization Ondansetron-more effective than antihistamine. Serotonin- antihistamine effect	Neuropathic element is cause of PB Pruritus and neuropeptide-mediated selective hyper innervation produces CNS excitement to develop longstanding symptoms of pruritus Needs more study

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(Goutos, Clarke, Upson, Richardson, & Ghosh, 2010)	Literature review Key variables: Pruritus, burn, itch, gabapentin, antihistamines	23 studies appraising therapeutic agents in the burns literature		TENS-effective in remodeling phase Multidisciplinary approach is needed in successful assessment & treatment. Employment of a tool to assess severity of pruritus is critical because sever pruritus needs a combination of agents- Itch man scale is recommended for burn patients Use of topical emollients & cooling agents is included in the protocol due to positive clinical experience even w/o supportive studies Agents acting on the central part of the pruritic pathway-gabapentin, ondasetron Agents acting on the peripheral part of the pruritic pathway-H1 partial agonist & H2 receptor antagonist Non-pharmacological adjunct-TENS, laser, pressure garment, massage therapy	The study advocates the early employment of centrally acting agents & peripherally acting agents as well as non-pharmacological interventions for the tx of PB pruritus
To review the current evidence on therapeutic agents for PB pruritus& use the GRADE classification to propose therapeutic protocols for adult & pediatric pts					
(Goutos, Dziewulski, & Richardson, 2009)	Literature review Key variables: PB pruritus			Therapeutic strategies are classified by interventions on peripheral & central aspects of the pruritic pathway Peripheral aspects: cooling of the wound, antihistamines, topical Doxepin, local anesthetics, colloidal oatmeal,	
To review effective					

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strategies to reduce PB pruritus				Capsaicin, Laser tx, Aloe Vera, topical Dapsone, Unna boot, Compression garments, Ondansteron Central aspects: Gabapentin, TENS, Massage therapy, Psychological support	
(Goutos, Eldardiri, Khan, Dziewulski, & Richardson, 2010) To compare gabapentin tx w/ antihistamine tx in acute PB pruritus	2 consecutive observational studies (using a stepwise approach for the tx of acute PB pruritus) Key variables: PB pruritus, acute burns, gabapentin, antihistamines	Study #1 50 PB pts applied to original St. Andrew's Anti-Itch Ladder Study #2 41 PB pts applied to revised St. Andrew's Anti-Itch Ladder EC: burn reconstruction surgery, known hypersensitivity to medicine in the protocol, epilepsy, or severe renal or hepatic impairment	Study #1 & #2 pts assessed for pruritic symptoms using "itch man scale" & VAS daily. VAS (0-4) 0: No itch 1: little itch not interfering w/ activity 2: more itch sometimes interfering w/activity 3: a lot of itch, which makes lying still & concentration difficulty 4: most terrible itch making it impossible to sit still & concentrate	Antipruritic monotherapy in acute burns: gabapentin monotherapy had 4 times more effective than chlorpheniramine tx (41.46% vs 10%) Antipruritic Polytherapy in acute burns: Combination of gabapentin, cetirizine, & cyproheptadine was more effective than combination of 3 antihistamines (chlorpheniramine, hydroxyzine, & cyproheptadine) in symptomatic relief of pruritus in PB population (95.12% vs 84%) Factors for failure in monotherapy are younger age and larger TBSA Pts w/ higher initial itch scores needed more pharmacologic escalation	Gabapentin is more effective as monotherapy by acting directly on the central nervous system It is important to use both central & peripheral aspects of the pruritic pathway in managing burns itching effectively Needs further studies incorporating long term f/u of comparing peripherally & centrally acting agents in late phases of wound healing
(Gu'rol, Polat, & Akcay, 2010)	Experimental study Key variables:	63 pts who admitted for burn tx in a large university	EG: 32, CG: 31. Demographically & burn characteristically no differences b/w EG & CG	EG showed significant improvement in reducing itching, pain, & anxiety compared to CG ($p < 0.001$)	Limits: small sample size, The study did not specify the condition of

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To examine if massage therapy reduced burned adolescents' pain, itching, & anxiety levels	Itching, pain, anxiety, massage therapy, adolescents	hospital from 2/2008 to 6/2009 IC: Aged 12-18, 2 nd or 3 rd degree burn, & no developmental problems or co-morbidity for inability to communicate	EG got 15minute massage tx 2x/wk for 5wks as well as standard care Massage tx done by trained massage therapists, applied to healthy skin around the wounds & surface of wound Itching rating, VAS for pain, & STAI assessed on the 1 st day & last day of 5-wk study period		wound whether it is healed or not. – it is assumed that not all wound are healed according to the fact some pts were getting standard tx including pain & they were enrolled in the study right after admission
(Hettrick, 2004) To evaluate the effect of TENS as the mgt of burn pruritus	A pilot study & RCT	11pts (CG) received only standard of care. 9pts (EG) received standard of care & TENS 1 hour a day, 7days per wk for 3wks. IC: age of 18-75 w/ partial or full-thickness burns, healed skin or required skin grafting, VAS >5, remodeling	VAS used by sample before & after tx and data were compared b/w 2 groups	TENS significantly reduced PB pruritus in the population sampled Therefore, TENS should be considered as a tx option for burn survivors whose quality of life is negatively affected by itching	Limits: Hard to generalized to children <18 or pts> 75yrs of age. The mode of TENS was high frequency & low-intensity mode Additional parameters for TENS need to be explored VAS varied by individuals. Can't apply to inflammatory or proliferative stage of wd healing.

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		phase of wd healing w/ recent re-epithelialization. EC: pregnancy, hx of epilepsy, pacemaker			
(Hultman, Edkins, Wu, Calvert, & Cairns, 2013) To evaluate effects of laser therapies on burn scars	Prospective, before-after, single cohort study Key variables: Burn injury, hypertrophic scar, laser tx	147 burn pts w/ hypertrophic burn scars All initially treated at the North Carolina Jaycee Burn Center	Sample: mean age-26.9, mean TBSA-16.1%, average 2.8sessions/pt, including pulsed dye laser & CO2 laser at 16months (median) & 48months (mean) after burn injury. VSS & UNC scar scale assessed right before the first session, 4-6wks later, & at the time of the next session	Within the 12months of the study period, VSS & UNC4P (pain, pruritus, pliability, & paresthesia) decreased ($P < 0.0001$)	Limits: 1.unaware of long-term effect 2.not specified in scar component 3.evaluator bias not excluded 4.no control group 5.order of different lasers not examined Recommendation: RCT w/ long-term period & objective data (elasticity, hardness, & redness) & subjective data (QoL)
(Jung et al., 2009) To see the effect of naltrexone as a potential antipruritic	Retrospective, experimental study Key variables: Naltrexone, itching	19 pts treated for burn injury at Hallym Burn Center of Hangyang Sacred Heart Hospital in Seoul, Korea.	Total 19pts (9-treated w/antihistamine only, 9-w/antihistamine & gabapentin, 1-w/gabapentin only) who are dissatisfied w/ current tx received naltrexone for 2wks. After 2wks, participants	14 pts reported improvement in experience of itching & 5 pts reported no change in itching 44.5% (9pts) reported ↓ scratching activity However, 7 pts reported side effects	Not sure of naltrexone as the first line of PB pruritus, but the study suggests naltrexone warrants further studies using RCT to examine its potential role as a tx for chronic itching in

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medication for burn pts experiencing chronic refractory itching		TBSA average: 40.32%, Average PBD before tx:157.3	answered for itching on VAS & compared w/retrospective rating of the severity of itching. (Tx: began w/25mg, then ↑ to 50mg the following day)	(headaches, nausea, vomiting, & abdominal cramps). No laboratory tests after tx noted	burn pts
(La Salle, Rachelska, & Nedelec, 2007) To evaluate the effect of Naltrexone in managing PB pruritus	Experimental study Key variables: Pruritus, Naltrexone, Burn injury	15 pts who were dissatisfied w/ traditional tx for PB pruritus. (from Villa medical Rehabilitation hospital) 2 dropped for side effect of naltrexone	15 pts who traditionally treated w/antihistamines (H1 or H2 receptor antagonist) & hydrating lotion, but still w/ pruritus recruited for naltrexone tx- 1pt dropped for allergic reaction, 1pt dropped for intolerable dizziness 8 pts completed French-Canadian version of the itch VAS before tx & 2wks after naltrexone tx, then compared the result. 5pts completed only after tx All pts answered 6 additional questions regarding naltrexone, too	Participants demonstrated some satisfaction of Naltrexone use in reducing PB pruritus; Overall, 50% (4pts) improved regarding frequency & duration of itching according to Frech-Canadian VAS questionnaire Regarding additional 6 questions, 72% (9pts) satisfied with the itch relief provided by naltrexone 62% (8pts) stated that QoL improved	Limits: Need a larger sample, More frequent measurement of itch intensity or qualification of scratching activity, recruitment of a broader range of burn pts, long term f/u, & a placebo controlled tx group needed
(Lewis et al., 2012) To test the	RCT, pilot & prospective study	52 burn pts treated b/w 3/10/08 & 7/22/08	Components of Medilixir-coconut, palm, castor, olive, hemp seed, wheat germ, & canola seed oil	1.Medilixir reduced itch after application more frequently than aqueous cream 2.By using Medilixir, pts felt itch	Medilixir is more effective to minimize PB pruritus than aqueous cream.

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efficacy of Medilixir (beeswax & herbal oil cream) compared to the standard tx of aqueous cream regarding relieving the PB itch symptoms	Key variables: PB itch, Beeswax, Herbal oils, Aqueous cream	Mean TBSA:7.2% IC: direct admission, age 18-80yrs, able to provide informed consent, & no allergy to Medilixir	Components of aqueous cream- paraffin, heavy liquid, phenoxyethanol, & purified water No significant difference in any demographics Mean time in seconds required for cream application & mean days before the 1 st cream application b/w two groups not significantly different. VAS used for itching	recurrence later than CG w/tx of aqueous cream 3.EG required less antipruritic medications than CG did	Limits: small sample size Meaning: a larger size study can be warranted
(Li-Sang, Lau, Choi, Chan, & Jianan, 2006) To determine the efficacy of silicone gel on severe post-traumatic hypertrophic scars among the Chinese population	RCT Silicone gel sheeting(SGS), Post traumatic hypertrophic scar, Thickness, Pain, itchness	45 Chinese pts w/ post-traumatic hypertrophic scars EG (24pts) wore SGS for 24hrs a day and received 15minute lanolin deep massage to the scar twice a day for 6months. CG (21pts) had only massage for the scar w/ the	Spectrocolorimeter & TUPS used for pigmentation measurement Vancouver Scar Scale for the scar thickness assessment VAS used for pain & itching Digital image of each scar was recorded by using a digital camera Two-way repeated	EG showed significant improvement regarding scar thickness & scar pliability For scar pigmentation, pain & itching, EG showed better outcomes but not significant	The study indicated that silicone gel sheeting was effective to reduce thickness, pain, itchiness, & pliability of the severe hypertrophic scar among the Chinese population Moisturization effect of the tough & hard scar may contribute to the reduction of the skin thickness after 6 months 's intervention

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		same frequency for 6months – 1pt dropped due to long traveling	ANOVA used to analyze above 4 measures & Turkey test for post hoc comparison analysis used for difference over time(2 & 6months after beginning) b/w 2groups		Limit: population is limited to Chinese people- generalization issue Small size of sample Study had only 16 burn scars out of 45 scars – can be applied to specifically to burn scar pts?
(Li-Tsang, Zheng, & Lau, 2010) To investigate the effect of pressure therapy (PG), silicone gel sheeting (SGS), & combined therapy (CT) on management of posttraumatic hypertrophic scar (HS)	RCT	104 subjects (M:63, F:41) recruited from Jiangsu People’s First Affiliated Hospital in Nanjing, China IC: Those w/ HS over limbs or body due to burns or traumatic injuries, & scar < 16cm ² EC: Those w/medical disease such as diabetes	4 groups of PG (n=30), SGS (n=24), combined w/ PG & SGS (CTG, n=29), & control group (CG, n=21) Drip-out: 20 pts 4 groups assessed before, 2, 4, & 6months after intervention Assessment tools: Subjective feedback from pts regarding their perception on the scar condition (cosmesis, pain, & pruritus) by VAS. Objective tools for scar-spectrocolorimeter (for color), TUPS (for thickness), & VSS (for pliability)	Scar Thickness: CTG showed significant improvement at 2, 4, 6 months after tx. PG showed significant improvement 6 months after tx. Scar Pigmentation: CTG showed more improvement than other groups & all other groups showed significant improvement regarding pigmentation over time Scar Pliability: significant improvement in all groups showed at each assessment. CTG had the most improvement in softness of scar among all groups at 2 & 4 months after tx Pain: 3 EG showed significantly less pain over time & CTG & PG had significant effect on pain	CTG & PG group showed significant improvement in scar thickness after 6months of intervention (CTG>PG). SGS showed more effective in decreasing pain and pruritus than the scar thickness Limits: high drop-rate (19.23%)

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		Criteria of HS: VSS > 5 & each subscore > 1		Pruritus: all groups reported significantly less itchy but SGS seemed better result (no significance)	
(Loey, Bremer, Faber, Middelkoop, & Nieuwenhuis, 2008) To study self-reported itching in a multicenter cohort among adults w/ burns at 3,12, & 24 months PB	Prospective, longitudinal & cohort study Key variables: Burns, PTSD, pruritus, psychological stress	510 PB pts admitted b/w 2/1997 & 1/2002 in 6 regional burn centers of Netherlands & Belgium 3months, 1yr, & 2yr f/u had 90% (460pts), 75% (380pts), & 42% (216pts), respectively	Questionnaires were completed by PB pts at 3months, 1yr, & 2yrs after burn accident The questionnaire has a 7-point Likert scale for itching & the Impact of Event Scale (IES) for assessing 2 symptoms of PTSD	Itching complaints at 3months, 1yr & 2yrs PB show 87%, 70% & 67%, respectively The frequency of moderate to severe itching is 34% & 23% at 1 & 2 yrs PB, respectively Risk factors for itching are surgical operations, PTS, gender (F>M) & TBSA However, TBSA is not a factor at 1 & 2yrs PB & gender is not a factor at 2yrs PB In conclusion, PTS symptoms & surgical operations (more grafted skin) are risk factors for itching at 2yrs PB	The study shows the necessity to approach itching from multiple perspectives, such as psychological state of pts, because chronic itching occurs in a group of different characteristics Limit: the questionnaire of the study is based on a single question. Answers were scored differently from VAS/ The study excluded pts w/ pre-accident psychiatric problems. The study may underestimate the prevalence rate of itching
(Mendham, 2004) To test the action of gabapentin on itching in	Experimental study Key variables: gabapentin, burn, itching	Sample size: Total 35 children (12>3yrs, 23≤3yrs). 3 out of 23 kids having skin loss from meningitis.	Gabapentin given starting as 5mg/kg tid. & maximum dose up to 5mg/kg bid & 10mg/kg at night.	Nurses and parents reported a remarkable reduction in itching & antihistamine intake was decreased or stopped	For children w/ behavioral difficulties, the tx needs to be cautiously used

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healing wounds in children admitted to the burn unit		All the sample treated w/ chlorpheniramine & trimeprazine before, but remained irritable & constantly rubbing wounds	-maximum dose for epilepsy:40mg/kg/day Parents & nursing staff assessed the effects of the tx (gabapentin use)	One child w/ ADHD showed disruptive behavior as a side effect-only one case	RCTs are necessary
(Nedelec, Rachelska, Parnell, & La Salle, 2012) Evaluating the effect of Provase® for pruritus relief in post burn population compared to a control moisturizer	Single site, prospective, double-blind, randomized, controlled, pilot Study IV: Provase, control moisturizer. DV: Pruritus	A total of 23 post burn patients who were itching from burn injury treated in Villa Medica Rehabilitation Hospital - 12 for tx group, 11 for control group. → 9 per each group completed the study IC: experiencing postburn pruritus at least 3 itch episodes during the past week with at least 2 itch episodes	Duration, frequency, & numbers of itch episode per day, itch TBSA & affective itch characteristics measured at baseline, 1,2,3, & 4 th wk after tx b/t control and tx groups 4 Measurement used: Description of Pruritus Experienced During Previous Week for Duration of episode – <5, ≥5 & <30, ≥30 & <60, or ≥60min Daily frequency – 0,1,2, or ≥3 Wkly frequency – b/t 1 & 7 days; Questionnaire for Pruritus Assessment for Burn Survivors;	Duration of itch episodes in minutes at baseline & wks 1, 2, 3, & 4. Tx group has shown significantly reduced duration of pruritus compared to the control group Frequency of itch was described as the number of days a wk at baseline, wks 1, 2, 3, & 4 showed that tx group had significantly low frequency at wks 2,3, & 4 compared to the control group Number of daily itch episodes was significantly lower in the tx group compared to the control group at wk 2 after the treatment Itch TBSA measurement over time for tx & control groups: Tx group had significantly smaller itch TBSA compared to the control group at wks 1, 2, & 3	Using Provase® significantly reduced burn associated pruritus compared to using other moisturizer Limitations: Small pilot study, single center & convenience population, short period of data collection (4wks), & no classification b/w acute & chronic pruritus in post burn population

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		during day & lasting more than 5 minutes, completely epithelialized test area, & 18 yrs or older	Modified Vancouver Scar Scale; Mexameter Descriptive statistics & a Wilcoxon rank-sum test used	Presence or absence of affective itch characteristics: Tx group significantly felt less bothersome from burn associated pruritus at wks 1, 2, 3, & 4, less annoyed at wks 4, & less unbearable from pruritus at wks 2, 3, & 4 compared to the control group	
(Ogawa & Hyakusoku, 2008) To attempt to use mugwort lotion for treating the itch associated w/ PB hypertrophic scars	Prospective, Cohort study Key variables: Mugwort lotion, Hypertrophic scars	15 pts (M5, F10; 24-74yrs old) w/ hypertrophic scars who suffered from 2 nd & 3 rd degree burns over average TBSA 35%	15pts received mugwort lotion twice a day, then 1 wk later survey completed. ; one pt was dropped for a cold sensation to the site of application. 2 months after the same tx, 14 pts completed survey regarding improvement of itching	No significant improvement after 1 wk of tx noted Significant improvement in pruritus, sleep disturbance & redness noted 2months after tx ($P = 0.027$)	Mugwort lotion is effective for improving subjective symptoms (itch & sleep disturbance) Need to continue to evaluate effects & mechanism of mugwort. Need to conduct more studies to evaluate this lotion
(Otene & Onumaegbu, 2013) Exploring the knowledge, attitudes & practices of Nigerian burn specialists & studying if there are	Descriptive study Questionnaire driven from 'Burns pruritus: A study of current practices in the UK' Goutos (2010)	35 PS who attended for 5 th conference in Nigeria (M:29, F:6) Conference name: joint scientific conferences and annual general meetings	Study subjects answered for: Q1. Time of the day when itching is most severe, Q2. Ages of experiencing more itch (adults or kids), Q3. Itch assessment tools in the greatest levels of pruritus, Q5. Treatment methods, usage of any form of anti-	Q1: 54.3%(night), 28.6% (afternoon), 2.9% (no difference), 14.3% (no answer) Q2: 34.3% (kids), 25.7% (adults), 25.7%(no difference), 14.3% (no difference) Q3: 88.6% (no assessment tool to use), 11.4% (vague methods used) Q4: 37.1% (deep dermal burns), 20% (partial thickness burns), 17.1% (full thickness burns), 11.4% (full thickness & deep dermal burns), 2.9% (partial	Itch man scale (0-4) recommended as assessment tool for pruritus & anti-pruritus regimen to be applied according to the scale Limitations: The recommendation needs to be supported by evidence based research. Sample size

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any uniform modalities of care for these patients, with the view of possibly providing standardization	Variables: post-burn pruritus, standardization	(AGM) of the Nigerian Association of Plastic, Reconstructive and Aesthetic Surgeons and the Nigerian Burns Society	pruritic regimen	thickness & deep dermal burns), 11.4% (no answer). 85.7% (conservative tx > skin graft tx) Q5: 57.1% (oral meds), 22.9% (Injections), 8.6% (topical agents), 5.7% (reassure pts), 5.7% (combination of oral & topical agents). 85.7% (no any form of anti-pruritic regimen).	too small & limited to a country (Nigeria) to generalize to the world
(Parnell, Nedelec, Rachelska, & LaSalle, 2012) Description & distinction of sustained postburn Pruritus	Cross-sectional study & prospective pilot study Key Variables: QoL, IF, II, pain, SC, scar, medication	23 subjects aged 18 yrs or older PB pruritus with the range from burn 1% to 15% TBSA Setting: during the clinical evaluation in Villa Medica Rehabilitation Hospital	Demographic findings: N = 23(M = 14,F = 9;19 = Caucasian) Mean years postburn (0.95), Range (0.1-3.21), Mean burn % TBSA (35.35), Mean pruritus %TBSA (6.22)-1 subject has 90% TBSA Scales & questionnaires in English & French; pain, pruritus, & QoL scales Parameter for acute pruritus & chronic pruritus d/f as persistent pruritus in PB subjects: PB 6months Primary variable analyzed as a single category	Frequency if pruritus: daily (87%) & 2-3x/wk (96%). Duration of pruritus per incidence: 5-30 minutes (52%)-No significant difference b/w acute & chronic pruritus groups Description of accompanying Sensation: Stinging (74%), pinching (48%), burning (43%); Crawling & burning pruritus sensation were perceived as more severe in spite of low frequencies Affective aspects of pruritus: Unbearable (91%), bothersome (91%), annoying (78%) Acute group has less pruritus episodes but more influence from the pruritus than chronic group Mean VAS Scores for Itch: 2.65. Worst pruritus score: 7 (acute group) & 9.07 (chronic group) Best score for pruritus: 1.38 There was a significant difference between the pruritus & pain sensations	First study to characterize nonstop PB pruritus Pruritus reported as unbearable, bothersome & annoying; Acute group reported more severe pruritus & it possibly expects that patients recover, improve coping skills & experience w/pruritus & scar maturation over time Acute pruritus group reported more pruritoceptive pruritus whereas chronic group reported more neuropathic pruritus. Therefore pruritic treatment can be more effective when pruritus

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			A severity index for sensation was calculated by 0, 1, 2 or 3	(general pain, $P = .0003$; local pain, $P = .0043$) Sleep problems associated with pruritus were not significantly reported Pruritus caused low concentration (N = 8), agitation (8), anxiety (4) & no change in the mood (6) Pruritus triggering QoL activities were dryness(83%), heat(70%), sweat(61%),activity(57%),stress(57%), fatigue(57%), physical effort(52%), & special fabric(48%) Cold temperature (30%), cold water (26%) & rest (22%) were pruritus relieving activities Sleep, lying down, sitting, eating & hot water did not affect pruritus. The severity scores of pruritus b/w scars were similar The natural lubrication of the skin b/w acute & chronic group was similar, but acute pruritus scars have more rough skin texture & higher mean level of erythema despite no significant differences b/w groups	characteristics are considered Pruritus triggering & relieving QoL activities reported, which can be applied to teach burn survivors to reduce pruritus episodes Limitations: ↓ power analysis d/t ↓sample size Acute pruritus period is broad The age of burn scars not specified Regulating the central sensitivity of pruritus explored incompletely-pruritus mechanisms & tx to be more studied Notes: Needs more pts from various areas, races, TBSA, & time after burn & research period to ↑ for generalizability
(Pfab et al., 2013)	Descriptive study	N/A	The article addressed CAM application and its effectiveness for atopic dermatitis, chronic urticaria, uremic itch,	Regarding pruritus in burns, 15 minute massage therapy twice a week over 5weeks reduced itching, pain, & anxiety levels in burn adolescents	This result is written just per two other articles that are included in the project

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To summarize current evidence, possible mechanisms, & clinical approaches for treating pruritus w/ CAM techniques	Key variables: pruritus, complementary, itch, acupuncture, alternative		postoperative itch, pruritus in burns, & intractable neuropathic itch		
(Ratcliff et al., 2005) Evaluate the effectiveness of a pharmacotherapeutic protocol for pain, anxiety, & itching	Retrospective chart review Key variables: pain, burn, children, morphine, acetaminophen, anxiety, benzodiazepines, itching, acute stress disorder	286 Acute burn children during 1/2001-12/2001 Shriners Hospitals for Children in Galveston, TX. 71% of samples less than 40%TBSA, 67% males, mean age 6.98 ± 5.2yrs, 58% Hispanic, average hospital stay days 11.1 ± 20.2days	The review done in terms of pain medication & TBSA, pain scales & age, medication given for PTSD, anxiety, itch & procedural pain, anxiety medication & TBSA, and itch medication & TBSA The review divided into 3 groups according to ages: <3, ≥3 to <10, & ≥10 Itch Man Scale used for pruritus degree	Findings only Relevant to itching written Performed per itching management as below; For itching > 2 of 4, give 1) Moisturizing body shampoo & lotions, topical ointments (not hydrocortisone creams) 2) Diphenhydramine 1.25mg/kg/dose po Q 6h 3) If itch remains poorly controlled, subsequently add hydroxyzine 0.6mg/kg/dose q 6h, then cyproheptadine 0.1mg/g/dose po q6h so that one of the medications is given q2hrs 39.2% received medication to control itching at the beginning, but eventually	Itching in children after-burn is a considerable problem and involves both grafted & non-grafted skin at a prevalence of up to 100% for the lower limbs Diphenhydramine was effective as a primary protocol medication for itching Other studies showed shower & bath oil containing liquid paraffin with 5% colloidal oatmeal, topically applied doxepin cream, &

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				all the children took some type of itch medication because their burn wounds got more itching as the course progressed.	cetirizine in combination with cimetidine were effective
(Richardson, Upton, & Rippon, 2014) Review of the tx of pruritus in people w/burn wounds	Literature review. Variables: burns, wound pruritus, itching, oral treatments, antihistamines .	Objectives of the study: identify various tx options, exploring the evidence base for each tx, Offering an algorithm based on best available evidence for wound r/t pruritus mgt	Literature review regarding PB pruritus relief mgt & synthesized findings	Below as effective txs for PB pruritus 1.Topical txs (cooling agents, colloidal oatmeal, topical emollients, mixture of beeswax & herbal oil, silicone gel sheeting, & EMLA). No significant difference for Capsaicin use 2.Oral txs (oral histamines, gabapentin, naltrexone, some antidepressants, & doxepin). Oral chemotherapy & topical immunosuppressants used for tx-resistant pruritus 3.Other txs (TENS, botulinum toxin, Unna's boot dressing, & nanocrystalline silver) 4.Psychological therapies Algorithm shown based on the stage of healing along with the algorithm by Brooks et al. (2008)	Good study due to the approach according to the phase of healing The suggested algorithm needs to be tried & evaluated effects of tx to generalize to all burn population
Roh et al., 2007) To verify the effect of SRMT on pruritus, skin status, & depression for Korean burn survivors	Pretest-posttest design SRMT, pruritus, Skin status, Depression, Burn survivors	2 skin rehabilitation clinics in Seoul, Korea b/w 11/2004 & 2/2005 Inclusion criteria: 18yrs and older, Partial or full thickness burn on	18 pts– SRMT group, 17 pts- control group Before SRMT & 3months after SRMT, survey for itching was completed. Burn scar & depression assessed by VSS & CES-D, respectively	SRMT significantly affected on burn scar healing positively SRMT significantly decreased depression among burn patients SRMT significantly decreased pruritus in burn victims There is a significant positive relationship among depression, objective skin status, and pruritus, too	The study is meaningful because massage therapy can have positive effects on pruritus, scar status, and depression among burn victims Limit: small sample size, needs more reliable & objective burn-scar

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		forearm or hand, & agreed to participate	Certified rehabilitation nurses applied SRMT 30 min/wk for 3 months & primary caregivers gave it 10min per day for 3 months		assessment tools
(Rowley-Conwy, 2014) To discuss the recent evidence in burn care, and the treatments and interventions that a pt may receive following a major burn injury	Review Key variables: Burn care, wound management, recovery, rehabilitation	Summarized the latest evidence in burn care by reviewing evidences regarding rehabilitation & recovery		For wound management: massage & emollients, topical silicone therapy, pressure garment therapy, low pulsed ultrasound, serial intralesional corticosteroid injections, laser therapy For chronic pain: analgesia For psychosocial care: long-term psychosocial follow up needed for PTSD For nutrition support: high calorie & protein with vitamins & minerals supplement Burn pruritus: massage w/ emollient cream, cool baths, pressure garments, & oral and topical antihistamines & analgesics	Limited exploration on post-burn pruritus management.-showing only general PB pruritus management w/o specific doses or frequencies
(Thompson et al., 2013) To explore relationship b/w HTP &	Prospective, single-blind, & cohort study? Key variables: HTS, itching,	300 pts w/.risk for developing HTS Blood drawn from pts & Pts seen 2 times (one	X 2 analysis was used. HTS is considered of VSS score > 7 VSS: Pigmentation(0-2), Vascularity (0-3), Pliability	Native American/Alaskan Native race, facial burns, & ≥ 20% TBSA burns are associated w/ ↑ risk of HTS development However, risk for itching is only associated with burn size ≥ 20% TBSA.	Limits: Relatively small cohort of 300subjects, No differences b/w VSS & itch scores in the subgroup while there is differences for the

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pruritus & pt's characteristics	pruritus	at 1-5months after burn, one at 6-12months after burn injury During two visits, VSS & itch scores were recorded	(0-5), Height (0-3)	There is no significant differences among ages and genders for both HTS & pruritus	entire population, There is no consensus in the literature as to what VSS score constitute hypertrophic scarring even if a VSS score of >7 was determined as a way of identifying HTS.
(Upton, Penn, Richardson, & Rippon, 2014) To explore the psychological tx options for pruritus in pts w/ wounds	Narrative design (78comprehensive narrative outlines of previously published information) Key variables: pruritus, itching, burn wound, psychological interventions	12 articles included IC: published b/w 1/1980 & 11/2013, written in English, contains itching in people w/wounds or mgt/tx of itching, or articles including skin disorders	Five psychological approaches to treat wound associated itching (Habit reversal, Suggestions, Relaxation training, Massage, & Itch-coping programs) reviewed from published literature	Habit reversal: itching is replaced by alternative behaviors using assessment, education & behavior analysis, and stimulation awareness training Suggestion: placebo effects have been effective in reducing itching & pain Relaxation training: many relaxation techniques have been effective to reduce itching (progressive muscle, biofeedback-assisted relaxation & heart rate variability biofeedback) Massage: massage techniques significantly decreased itching, pain, anxiety, skin status, remaining, depression, skin pigmentation, pliability, vascularity, & height	A number of psychological tx can be used for pts w/ pruritus –Habit reversal, Suggestions, Relaxation training, Massage, & Itch-coping programs Limit: researches are relatively weak from low sample sizes, lack of control groups & randomization
(Waked, Nagib, & Ashm, 2013)	RCT Key variables: triamcinolone	Group1:20pts received tens, Group2:20pts received	5-D Itch scale used to assess five domains of degree, duration, direction, disability, and distribution	There is a significant difference b/w pre and post tx in both group1 & group2 regarding pruritus (P<0.05)	Triamcinolone acetonide phonophoresis is as useful as TENS to

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To evaluate the effectiveness of triamcinolone acetonide phonophoresis versus TENS in the tx of PB pruritus	acetonide, phonophoresis, TENS, PB pruritus, 5D Itch Scale, VSS	triamcinolone acetonide phonophoresis. Period: 10/2009-9/2010 IC:age:18-50yrs, 2 nd & 3 rd degree burn, TBSA of 10-15%, itching>5min & annoying EC: Non-burn origin pruritus, liver, thyroid, & kidney disease, DM, pregnancy, open wound, sensitivity to cortisone, pacemakers, skin malignancy, taking glucocorticoids, phototoxic or immunosuppressive medicine	of itching Mann-Whiney U test used to assess b/w 2 groups Wilcoxon test used to assess parameters within each group Student t-test used to assess the difference in the parameters All P values < 0.05	There is no significant differences b/w 2groups regarding effect of pruritus reduction	reduce PB pruritus Limits: No control group in the study & small sample noted Suggestion: further studies to compare control group with both tx (Triamcinolone acetonide phonophoresis & TENS)
(Warner, Coffee, & Yowler, 2014) To support	Review Key variables: pruritus, burn, outpatient	Summarized burn wound, pain management, home car instructions,		Early pruritus management: histamine H-1 receptor blocking agent (cetirizine) on as scheduled basis not as needed basis combined with frequent massage of moisturizers	Not mentioned specific dosages or frequency of tx for PB pruritus, but scheduled use of antihistamine is notable

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efficient outpatient burn management	care	outpatient clinic follow-up & outpatient management of complications (pain, pruritus, infection)		In addition, neuro-inflammatory transmitter blockers (gabapentin & pregabalin) is effective because itch-specific neurons won't be stimulated by these transmitters by using this medicine	
(Whitaker, 2001) To see the effect of TENS in reducing PB pruritus	Case study Key variables: TENS, pruritus, burns	A 19 yr old pt w/70% mixed thickness flame burns. Once healed, pt had severe itching & TENS applied to relieve pruritus resulting from burns	Pt received TENS 9hrs a day for 2wks Assessment for itching done daily for 5days, at 9 th day, & 16 th day after tx Pt did not receive TENS after 2wks d/t no itching	Day#1: 62.5% reduction in itching within 4hrs of application Day#2: 88% reduction within 4hrs of application Day#3 – the end of study (DAY#16): No itching within 4hrs of application	A larger case study or full-scale study needed
(Yang et al., 2014) To evaluate the manifestation of TRP channels in post-burn pruritus in order to help determine a specific therapeutic approach for post-burn	Key variables: burn, pruritus, TRPA1, TRPV3, TRPV4.	51 (F:14, M:37) burn patients with scars with ages ranging 8 - 60yrs	Group A: 33pts w/pruritus, Group B: 18pts w/o pruritus Differences b/w groups: Group A has thicker burn scars, more TBSA, more male population, & higher numbers in scar assessment than Group B	Histopathological analysis result: Group A has less elastic fibers (density) than Group B Immunoreactivity of TRP channels in burn scar & normal skin result: TRPV3, TRPV4, & TRPA1 elevated in Group A's scar tissue	Patient with post burn pruritus had broader burned areas & more severe scars They also had elevated TPRV3, TPRV4, & TPRA1 in the skin TRPV4 becomes more active at temperature > 25°C & by arachidonic acid Treatment w/ antagonist of TRPA1 & TRPV4

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pruritus					for this population will be meaningful in the future
(Zachariah et al., 2011) To review current tx options for PB pruritus	Review article Key variables: PB pruritus, Literature review, Gabapentin, Pruritus pathway.			Current tx options for PB pruritus: Antihistamines (H1 & H2 receptor antagonists), Topical alternatives over the healed burn wounds (colloidal oatmeal baths, EMLA, corticosteroids, massage therapy, Doxepin cream), Adjuncts (Biofeedback therapy, psychological support, combined w/pharmacological agents, TENS), Newer medicine: Ondansetron (5HT-3 receptor antagonist), Gabapentin (anti-epileptic drug), Pregabalin (anti-convulsant), Paroxetine (SSRI), & Naltrexone (opioid antagonist)	Use of gabapentin showed excellent relief in PB pruritus, especially tolerated well in children w/o significant side effects, which can be the 2 nd choice for the case of antihistamine resistant & failure

ABSHS = Abbreviated Burn Specific Health Scale; ACD = allergic contact dermatitis; AD = atopic dermatitis; ADHD = attention deficit hyperactivity disorder; BDISF = Beck Depression Inventory-Short Form; bid = twice a day; b/w = between; CAM = complementary and alternative medicine; CG = control group; CLD = cholestatic liver diseases; c/o = complain of; CTD = connective tissue disease; CU = chronic urticaria; CV = confounding variable; CVD = cardiovascular disease; D/C = Discharge; d/f = defined; DFS = Dutch Fatigue Scale; DM = diabetes mellitus; d/t = due to; DV(s) = dependent variable(s); EC = exclusion criteria; EG = experimental group; EMLA = eutectic mixture of local anesthetic; F = female; f/u = follow up; G = group; GRADE = Grading of Recommendations, Assessment, Development and Evaluation; HD = hemodialysis; HS = hypertrophic scar; ht = height; HTP = hypertrophic scar; hx = history; IC = inclusion criteria; IF = itch frequency; II = itch intensity; info = information; IV(s) = independent variable(s); LAS = Linear Analog Scale; LIS = Leuven Itch Scale; LTF = Long-Term Follow up; M = male; meds = medications; Mexameter = a tristimulus colorimeter device used to measure scar; mgt = management; MRI = magnetic resonance image; MVLR = multivariate logistic regression analysis; mVSS = modified Vancouver Scar Scale; N = Number; NIDRR BMS = National Institute on Disability & Rehabilitation Research Burn Model System; NRS = Numeric Rating Scale; P1 = initial version; P2 = second version; P3 = third version; P4 = fourth version; PB = postburn; PBD = post burn days; P/E = physical examination; PET = positron emission tomography; PG = pressure therapy; PS = plastic surgeon; PSS = Perceived Stress Scale; pt = patient; PTS = post-traumatic stress; PTSD = post-traumatic stress disorder; QD = daily; QoL = quality of life; RCT = randomized clinical trial; r/t = related to; SC = skin condition; SGS = silicone gel sheeting; SLS = Satisfaction with Life Scale; SSRI = selective serotonin reuptake inhibitor; STAI = State Trait Anxiety Inventory; SWL = satisfaction with life; TBSA = total body surface area; TENS = transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation; TEWL = transepidermal

water loss; tid = three times a day; TRP = transient receptor potential; TRPA = transient receptor potential ankyrin; TRPV = transient receptor potential vanilloid; TUPS = tissue ultrasound palpation system; tx = treatment; UNC = University of North Carolina; USG = ultrasonography; VAS = visual analog scale; vs = versus; v/s = vital signs; VSS = Vancouver Scar Scale; Wd = wound; wks = weeks; w/ = with; w/o = without; yrs = years.

- Articles are organized by the last name of the first author of each article.